

Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

The idea of *nested magic squares* is well known in the literature, generally known by *bordered magic squares*. Instead, considering entries as consecutive numbers, we considered consecutive odd numbers entries. This gives us *perfect square sum magic squares*. We worked with magic squares of orders 3 to 25. Finally, the result can be written in a symmetric way, i.e., $T_{m \times k} := m^2 \times k^2$, where m is the order of *nested magic square*, k is the order of *sub-magic squares* in each case, and T is the total entries sum. Also the entries sums are connected with *Pythagorean triples* and borders. In each case, the *difference among consecutive borders sums* is always a fixed value.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Nested Magic Squares	3
2.1	Magic Square of Order 3	3
2.2	Magic Square of Order 4	3
2.3	Nested Magic Square of Order 5	4
2.4	Nested Magic Square of Order 6	5
2.5	Nested Magic Square of Order 7	6
2.6	Nested Magic Square of Order 8	7
2.7	Nested Magic Square of Order 9	8
2.8	Nested Magic Square of Order 10	10
2.9	Nested Magic Square of Order 11	12
2.10	Nested Magic Square of Order 12	13
2.11	Nested Magic Square of Order 13	15
2.12	Nested Magic Square of Order 14	18
2.13	Nested Magic Square of Order 15	20
2.14	Nested Magic Square of Order 16	22
2.15	Nested Magic Square of Order 17	24
2.16	Nested Magic Square of Order 18	27
2.17	Nested Magic Square of Order 19	29
2.18	Nested Magic Square of Order 20	32
2.19	Nested Magic Square of Order 21	35
2.20	Nested Magic Square of Order 22	38
2.21	Nested Magic Square of Order 23	41
2.22	Nested Magic Square of Order 24	45
2.23	Nested Magic Square of Order 25	48

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978); E-mail: ijjtaneja@gmail.com; Web-site: <https://inderjtaneja.com>; Twitter: @IJTANEJA; Instagram: @crazynumbers.

3 Simplified Procedure	51
3.1 Even Order Nested Magic Squares	51
3.2 Odd Order Nested Magic Squares	54
4 Final Results	57

1 Introduction

It is well-known that sum of **odd numbers series** is given by

$$F_n := 1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + (2n - 1) = n^2, n \in N_+ \tag{1}$$

Since, we are working with magic squares, let's write $n = k^2$. This gives

$$F_{k^2} = F(k) := 1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + (2k^2 - 1) = k^4, k \in N_+ \tag{2}$$

The number k is the order of the magic square. Thus for all $k \geq 3$, we can always have a consecutive odd numbers magic square with sum entries a perfect square.

Let's write last member of (1) as m , then $n = \frac{m+1}{2}$. This gives

$$F(m) := 1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + m = \left(\frac{m+1}{2}\right)^2, m \in N_+ \tag{3}$$

The magic square sum of order n is given

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{4}$$

The sum of all entries of a magic square of order n is given by

$$T_{n \times n} := \frac{n^2 \times (n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{5}$$

According to (2), if the entries are consecutive odd numbers starting from one, then $T_{n \times n} := n^4$, i.e., entries sum is forth power of order of magic square.

The aim of this work is to consider consecutive odd numbers to bring total sums entries as perfect square sums for the **nested magic squares**. Also to show that these entries sums satisfy **Pythagorean triple properties**. Results on **borders** values are also studied. The whole work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 25.

There are many types of **bordered magic squares**. Here we are working with bordered magic squares, where one is contained in another, just as sub-magic squares. Due to this we called this category as **nested magic squares**. For study in this direction, refer to [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11].

2 Nested Magic Squares

This section brings **nested magic squares** of orders 3 to 25 for the consecutive odd order entries starting from 1. It is shown that the entries sums are related with Pythagorean triples. Also, it is shown that there is a constant difference among the **consecutive magic squares** entries. This study we called as **borders values**. We start with magic squares of orders 3 and 4, but we don't have nested property as there are no magic squares of orders 1 and 2. The **nested magic squares** for consecutive natural numbers can be obtained from the site H. White's site [1]. Here we modified it for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries.

2.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 2.1. Let's consider a magic square of order 3 formed by 9 consecutive odd positive natural numbers $\{1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17\}$ given by

			27
3	13	11	27
17	9	1	27
7	5	15	27
27	27	27	27

Sum of total entries is given by

$$T_{3 \times 3} := 3 \times 27 = 81 = 9^2.$$

According to formula (3),

$$T_{3 \times 3} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 25 + 27 = \left(\frac{17 + 1}{2} \right)^2 = 9^2 = 3^4.$$

2.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Example 2.2. Let's consider a magic square of order 4 formed by 16 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 29, 31\}$ given by

				64
27	1	7	29	64
13	23	17	11	64
21	15	9	19	64
3	25	31	5	64
64	64	64	64	64

Sum of total entries is given by

$$T_{4 \times 4} := 4 \times 64 = 256 = 16^2 = 4^2 \times 4^2.$$

Alternatively,

$$T_{4 \times 4} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 29 + 31 = \left(\frac{31 + 1}{2} \right)^2 = 16^2 = 4^4.$$

2.3 Nested Magic Square of Order 5

Example 2.3. Let's consider a nested magic square of order 5 formed by 25 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 47, 49\}$:

					125
43	35	5	3	39	125
13	19	29	27	37	125
9	33	25	17	41	125
49	23	21	31	1	125
11	15	45	47	7	125
	125	125	125	125	125

The above nested magic square of order 5 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 13, 15, D_{3 \times 3}, 35, 37, \dots, 47, 49\} \\
 &\dots \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 75 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 125.
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (6), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 17 + 19 + \dots + 31 + 33 = \left(\frac{33+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{15+1}{2}\right)^2 = 17^2 - 8^2 = 15^2 = 5^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 47 + 49 = \left(\frac{49+1}{2}\right)^2 = 25^2 = 5^2 \times 5^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.1. The nested magic square of order 5 formed by 25 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 47, 49\}$ satisfy the following properties:

- i. The entries sum of magic square of order 3 nested in a magic square of order 5 satisfies **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e., $T_{5 \times 5} := 15^2 = 17^2 - 8^2$;
- ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 5 is forth power of 5, i.e., $T_{5 \times 5} := 5^4$;
- iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to order of magic squares, i.e., $T_{3 \times 3} := 5^2 \times 3^2$ and $T_{5 \times 5} := 5^2 \times 5^2$.
- iv. The **borders** sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 5^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 400 = 5^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 5^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 200 = 5^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 25$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the difference among the **borders** values is $d_{border} := 200$.

2.4 Nested Magic Square of Order 6

Example 2.4. Let's consider a *nested magic square* of order 6 formed by 36 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 69, 71\}$ given by

						216
61	13	67	1	65	9	216
55	47	21	27	49	17	216
19	33	43	37	31	53	216
15	41	35	29	39	57	216
3	23	45	51	25	69	216
63	59	5	71	7	11	216
216	216	216	216	216	216	216

The above *nested magic square* of order 6 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\}$$

$$D_{6 \times 6} := \{1, 3, \dots, 17, 19, D_{4 \times 4}, 53, 55, \dots, 69, 71\}$$

... (7)

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 144$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 216.$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (7), we get

$$T_{4 \times 4} := 21 + 23 + \dots + 49 + 51 = \left(\frac{51+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{19+1}{2}\right)^2 = 26^2 - 10^2 = 24^2 = 6^2 \times 4^2$$

$$T_{6 \times 6} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 69 + 71 = \left(\frac{71+1}{2}\right)^2 = 36^2 = 6^2 \times 6^2.$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.2. The nested magic square of order 6 formed by 36 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 69, 71\}$ satisfy the following properties:

- i. The entries sum of magic square of order 4 nested in a magic square of order 6 satisfies **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e., $T_{4 \times 4} := 24^2 = 26^2 - 10^2$;
- ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 6 is forth power of 6, i.e., $T_{6 \times 6} := 6^4$;
- iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to order of magic squares, i.e., $T_{4 \times 4} := 6^2 \times 4^2$ and $T_{6 \times 6} := 6^2 \times 6^2$.
- iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$B_{6 \times 6} := T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 8^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 720 = 6^2 \times 4 \times 5$$

$$B_{4 \times 4} := T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 6^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 432 = 6^2 \times 4 \times 3,$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 29 + 35 + 37 + 43 = 144$ are four central values of *nested magic square*. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 288 = 2 \times 4 \times 6^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 144$. This gives $432 - 144 = 288$, the same constant value.

2.5 Nested Magic Square of Order 7

Example 2.5. Let's consider a *nested magic square* of order 7 formed by 49 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 95, 97\}$ given by

							343
83	3	7	9	79	75	87	343
77	67	59	29	27	63	21	343
81	37	43	53	51	61	17	343
85	33	57	49	41	65	13	343
5	73	47	45	55	25	93	343
1	35	39	69	71	31	97	343
11	95	91	89	19	23	15	343
	343	343	343	343	343	343	343

The above *nested magic square* of order 7 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{41, 43, \dots, 55, 57\}$$

$$D_{5 \times 5} := \{25, 27, \dots, 37, 39, D_{3 \times 3}, 59, 61, \dots, 71, 73\}$$

$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{1, 3, \dots, 21, 23, D_{5 \times 5}, 75, 77, \dots, 95, 97\}$$

... (8)

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 147$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 245$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 343.$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (8), we get

$$T_{3 \times 3} := 41 + 43 + \dots + 55 + 57 = \left(\frac{57+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{39+1}{2}\right)^2 = 29^2 - 20^2 = 21^2 = 7^2 \times 3^2$$

$$T_{5 \times 5} := 25 + 27 + \dots + 71 + 73 = \left(\frac{73+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{23+1}{2}\right)^2 = 37^2 - 12^2 = 35^2 = 7^2 \times 5^2$$

$$T_{7 \times 7} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 95 + 97 = \left(\frac{97+1}{2}\right)^2 = 49^2 = 7^2 \times 7^2.$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.3. The nested magic square of order 7 formed by 49 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 95, 97\}$ satisfy the following properties:

- i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3 and 5 nested in a magic square of order 7 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e., $T_{3 \times 3} := 21^2 = 29^2 - 20^2$ and $T_{5 \times 5} := 35^2 = 37^2 - 12^2$;

- ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 7 is forth power of 7, i.e., $T_{7 \times 7} := 7^4$;
- iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e., $T_{3 \times 3} := 7^2 \times 3^2$, $T_{5 \times 5} := 7^2 \times 5^2$ and $T_{7 \times 7} := 7^2 \times 7^2$..
- iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 7^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 1176 = 7^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 7^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 784 = 7^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 7^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 392 = 7^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 49$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 392$.

2.6 Nested Magic Square of Order 8

Example 2.6. Let's consider a *nested magic square* of order 8 formed by 64 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 125, 127\}$ given by

								512
115	125	5	1	27	103	23	113	512
109	89	41	95	29	93	37	19	512
111	83	75	49	55	77	45	17	512
121	47	61	71	65	59	81	7	512
21	43	69	63	57	67	85	107	512
11	31	51	73	79	53	97	117	512
9	91	87	33	99	35	39	119	512
15	3	123	127	101	25	105	13	512
512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512

The above *nested magic square* of order 8 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{49, 51, \dots, 77, 79\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{29, 31, \dots, 45, 47, D_{4 \times 4}, 81, 83, \dots, 97, 99\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 25, 27, D_{6 \times 6}, 101, 103, \dots, 125, 127\} \\
 &\dots \tag{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 256 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 384 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 512.
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (9), we get

$$T_{4 \times 4} := 49 + 51 + \dots + 77 + 79 = \left(\frac{79+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{47+1}{2}\right)^2 = 40^2 - 24^2 = 32^2 = 8^2 \times 4^2$$

$$T_{6 \times 6} := 29 + 31 + \dots + 97 + 99 = \left(\frac{99+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{27+1}{2}\right)^2 = 50^2 - 14^2 = 48^2 = 8^2 \times 6^2$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 125 + 127 = \left(\frac{127+1}{2}\right)^2 = 64^2 = 8^2 \times 8^2.$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.4. *The nested magic square of order 8 formed by 64 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 125, 127\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

- i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4 and 6 nested in a magic square of order 8 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e., $T_{4 \times 4} := 32^2 = 40^2 - 24^2$ and $T_{6 \times 6} := 48^2 = 50^2 - 14^2$;*
- ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 8 is forth power of 8, i.e., $T_{8 \times 8} := 8^4$;*
- iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e., $T_{4 \times 4} := 8^2 \times 4^2$, $T_{6 \times 6} := 8^2 \times 6^2$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 8^2 \times 8^2$.*
- iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$B_{8 \times 8} := T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 8^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 1792 = 8^2 \times 4 \times 7$$

$$B_{6 \times 6} := T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 8^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 1280 = 8^2 \times 4 \times 5$$

$$B_{4 \times 4} := T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 8^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 768 = 8^2 \times 4 \times 3,$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 57 + 63 + 65 + 71 = 256$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 512 = 2 \times 4 \times 8^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 512$. This gives $768 - 256 = 512$, the same constant value.

2.7 Nested Magic Square of Order 9

Example 2.7. *Let's consider a **nested magic square** of order 9 formed by 81 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 159, 161\}$ given by*

									729
143	3	7	11	13	139	135	131	147	729
133	115	35	39	41	111	107	119	29	729
137	109	99	91	61	59	95	53	25	729
141	113	69	75	85	83	93	49	21	729
145	117	65	89	81	73	97	45	17	729
9	37	105	79	77	87	57	125	153	729
5	33	67	71	101	103	63	129	157	729
1	43	127	123	121	51	55	47	161	729
15	159	155	151	149	23	27	31	19	729
	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729

The above *nested magic square* of order 9 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{73, 75, \dots, 87, 89\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{57, 59, \dots, 69, 71, D_{3 \times 3}, 91, 93, \dots, 103, 105\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{33, 35, \dots, 53, 55, D_{5 \times 5}, 107, 109, \dots, 127, 129\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 29, 31, D_{7 \times 7}, 131, 133, \dots, 159, 161\} \\
 &\dots \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 243 & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 567 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 405 & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 729.
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (10), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 73 + 75 + \dots + 87 + 89 = \left(\frac{89+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{71+1}{2}\right)^2 = 45^2 - 36^2 = 27^2 = 9^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 57 + 59 + \dots + 103 + 105 = \left(\frac{105+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{55+1}{2}\right)^2 = 53^2 - 28^2 = 45^2 = 9^2 \times 5^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 33 + 35 + \dots + 127 + 129 = \left(\frac{129+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{31+1}{2}\right)^2 = 65^2 - 16^2 = 63^2 = 9^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 159 + 161 = \left(\frac{161+1}{2}\right)^2 = 81^2 = 9^2 \times 9^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.5. The nested magic square of order 9 formed by 81 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 159, 161\}$ satisfy the following properties:

- i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5 and 7 nested in a magic square of order 9 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e., $T_{3 \times 3} := 27^2 = 45^2 - 36^2$, $T_{5 \times 5} := 45^2 = 53^2 - 28^2$ and $T_{7 \times 7} := 63^2 = 65^2 - 16^2$;
- ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 9 is forth power of 9, i.e., $T_{9 \times 9} := 9^4$;
- iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e., $T_{3 \times 3} := 9^2 \times 3^2$, $T_{5 \times 5} := 9^2 \times 5^2$, $T_{7 \times 7} := 9^2 \times 7^2$ and $T_{9 \times 9} := 9^2 \times 9^2$.
- iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{9 \times 9} &:= T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 9^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 2592 = 9^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 9^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 1944 = 9^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 9^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 1296 = 9^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 9^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 648 = 9^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 81$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 648$.

2.8 Nested Magic Square of Order 10

Example 2.8. Let's consider a **nested magic square** of order 10 formed by 100 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 197, 199\}$ given by

181	171	31	167	35	27	7	195	3	183	1000
25	151	161	41	37	63	139	59	149	175	1000
177	145	125	77	131	65	129	73	55	23	1000
21	147	119	111	85	91	113	81	53	179	1000
191	157	83	97	107	101	95	117	43	9	1000
1	57	79	105	99	93	103	121	143	199	1000
185	47	67	87	109	115	89	133	153	15	1000
13	45	127	123	69	135	71	75	155	187	1000
189	51	39	159	163	137	61	141	49	11	1000
17	29	169	33	165	173	193	5	197	19	1000
1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000

The above **nested magic square** of order 10 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{85, 87, \dots, 113, 115\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{65, 67, \dots, 81, 83, D_{4 \times 4}, 117, 119, \dots, 133, 135\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{37, 39, \dots, 61, 63, D_{6 \times 6}, 137, 139, \dots, 161, 163\} \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 33, 35, D_{8 \times 8}, 165, 167, \dots, 197, 199\}
 \end{aligned}$$

... (11)

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned} S_{4 \times 4} &:= 400 \\ S_{6 \times 6} &:= 600 \\ S_{8 \times 8} &:= 800 \\ S_{10 \times 10} &:= 1000. \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (11), we get

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4 \times 4} &:= 85 + 87 + \dots + 113 + 115 = \left(\frac{115+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{83+1}{2}\right)^2 = 58^2 - 42^2 = 40^2 = 10^2 \times 4^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} &:= 65 + 67 + \dots + 133 + 135 = \left(\frac{135+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{63+1}{2}\right)^2 = 68^2 - 32^2 = 60^2 = 10^2 \times 6^2 \\ T_{8 \times 8} &:= 37 + 39 + \dots + 161 + 163 = \left(\frac{163+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{35+1}{2}\right)^2 = 82^2 - 18^2 = 80^2 = 10^2 \times 8^2 \\ T_{10 \times 10} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 197 + 199 = \left(\frac{199+1}{2}\right)^2 = 100^2 = 10^2 \times 10^2. \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.6. The nested magic square of order 10 formed by 100 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 197, 199\}$ satisfy the following properties:

- i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 nested in a magic square of order 10 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e., $T_{4 \times 4} := 40^2 = 58^2 - 42^2$, $T_{6 \times 6} := 60^2 = 68^2 - 32^2$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 80^2 = 82^2 - 18^2$;
- ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 10 is forth power of 10, i.e., $T_{10 \times 10} := 10^4$;
- iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e., $T_{4 \times 4} := 10^2 \times 4^2$, $T_{6 \times 6} := 10^2 \times 6^2$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 10^2 \times 8^2$ and $T_{10 \times 10} := 10^2 \times 10^2$.
- iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned} B_{10 \times 10} &:= T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 10^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 3600 = 10^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\ B_{8 \times 8} &:= T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 10^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 2800 = 10^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\ B_{6 \times 6} &:= T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 10^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 2000 = 10^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\ B_{4 \times 4} &:= T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 10^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 1200 = 10^2 \times 4 \times 3, \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 93 + 99 + 101 + 107 = 400$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 800 = 2 \times 4 \times 10^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 400$. This gives $1200 - 400 = 800$, the same constant value.

2.9 Nested Magic Square of Order 11

Example 2.9. Let's consider a *nested magic square* of order 11 formed by 121 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 239, 241\}$ given by

											1331
19	1	5	9	13	221	217	213	209	205	219	1331
239	183	43	47	51	53	179	175	171	187	3	1331
235	173	155	75	79	81	151	147	159	69	7	1331
231	177	149	139	131	101	99	135	93	65	11	1331
227	181	153	109	115	125	123	133	89	61	15	1331
225	185	157	105	129	121	113	137	85	57	17	1331
27	49	77	145	119	117	127	97	165	193	215	1331
31	45	73	107	111	141	143	103	169	197	211	1331
35	41	83	167	163	161	91	95	87	201	207	1331
39	55	199	195	191	189	63	67	71	59	203	1331
23	241	237	233	229	21	25	29	33	37	223	1331
1331	1331	1331	1331	1331	1331	1331	1331	1331	1331	1331	1331

The above *nested magic square* of order 11 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{113, 115, \dots, 127, 129\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{97, 99, \dots, 109, 111, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 131, 133, \dots, 143, 145\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{73, 75, \dots, 93, 95, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 147, 149, \dots, 167, 169\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{41, 43, \dots, 69, 71, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 171, 173, \dots, 199, 201\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 37, 39, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 203, 205, \dots, 239, 241\} \\
 &\dots \tag{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 363 & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1089 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 605 & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 1331. \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 847
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (12), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 113 + 115 + \dots + 127 + 129 = \left(\frac{129+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{111+1}{2}\right)^2 = 65^2 - 56^2 = 33^2 = 11^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 97 + 99 + \dots + 143 + 145 = \left(\frac{145+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{95+1}{2}\right)^2 = 73^2 - 48^2 = 55^2 = 11^2 \times 5^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 73 + 75 + \dots + 167 + 169 = \left(\frac{169+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{71+1}{2}\right)^2 = 85^2 - 36^2 = 77^2 = 11^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 41 + 43 + \dots + 199 + 201 = \left(\frac{201+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{39+1}{2}\right)^2 = 101^2 - 20^2 = 99^2 = 11^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 239 + 241 = \left(\frac{241+1}{2}\right)^2 = 121^2 = 11^2 \times 11^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.7. *The nested magic square of order 11 formed by 121 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 239, 241\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 nested in a magic square of order 11 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 33^2 = 65^2 - 56^2 & T_{7 \times 7} &:= 77^2 = 85^2 - 36^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 55^2 = 73^2 - 48^2 & T_{9 \times 9} &:= 99^2 = 101^2 - 20^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 11 is forth power of 11, i.e., $T_{11 \times 11} := 11^4$;*

iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 11^2 \times 3^2 & T_{7 \times 7} &:= 11^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 11^2 \times 5^2 & T_{9 \times 9} &:= 11^2 \times 9^2 \\
 & & T_{11 \times 11} &:= 11^2 \times 11^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{11 \times 11} &:= T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{11 \times 11} - S_{9 \times 9}) = 11^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 4840 = 11^2 \times 2^3 \times 5 \\
 B_{9 \times 9} &:= T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 11^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 3872 = 11^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 11^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 2904 = 11^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 11^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 1936 = 11^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 11^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 968 = 11^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 121$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 968$.

2.10 Nested Magic Square of Order 12

Example 2.10. *Let's consider a nested magic square of order 12 formed by 144 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 285, 287\}$ given by*

265	257	259	27	25	11	33	269	271	15	275	21	1728
35	225	215	75	211	79	71	51	239	47	227	253	1728
251	69	195	205	85	81	107	183	103	193	219	37	1728
39	221	189	169	121	175	109	173	117	99	67	249	1728
247	65	191	163	155	129	135	157	125	97	223	41	1728
43	235	201	127	141	151	145	139	161	87	53	245	1728
1	45	101	123	149	143	137	147	165	187	243	287	1728
9	229	91	111	131	153	159	133	177	197	59	279	1728
281	57	89	171	167	113	179	115	119	199	231	7	1728
5	233	95	83	203	207	181	105	185	93	55	283	1728
285	61	73	213	77	209	217	237	49	241	63	3	1728
267	31	29	261	263	277	255	19	17	273	13	23	1728
1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728

The above *nested magic square* of order 12 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{129, 131, \dots, 157, 159\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{109, 111, \dots, 125, 127, D_{4 \times 4}, 161, 163, \dots, 177, 179\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{81, 83, \dots, 105, 107, D_{6 \times 6}, 181, 183, \dots, 205, 207\} \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{45, 47, \dots, 77, 79, D_{8 \times 8}, 209, 211, \dots, 241, 243\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 41, 43, D_{10 \times 10}, 245, 247, \dots, 285, 287\} \\
 &\dots \tag{13}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 576 & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 1440 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 864 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 1728. \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 1152
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (13), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 129 + 131 + \dots + 157 + 159 = \left(\frac{159 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{127 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 80^2 - 64^2 = 48^2 = 12^2 \times 4^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 109 + 111 + \dots + 177 + 179 = \left(\frac{179 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{107 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 90^2 - 54^2 = 72^2 = 12^2 \times 6^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 81 + 83 + \dots + 205 + 207 = \left(\frac{207 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{79 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 104^2 - 40^2 = 96^2 = 12^2 \times 8^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 45 + 47 + \dots + 241 + 243 = \left(\frac{243 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{43 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 122^2 - 22^2 = 120^2 = 12^2 \times 10^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$T_{12 \times 12} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 285 + 287 = \left(\frac{287 + 1}{2} \right)^2 = 144^2 = 12^2 \times 12^2.$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.8. *The nested magic square of order 12 formed by 144 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 285, 287\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 nested in a magic square of order 12 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4 \times 4} &:= 48^2 = 80^2 - 64^2 & T_{8 \times 8} &:= 96^2 = 104^2 - 40^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} &:= 72^2 = 90^2 - 54^2 & T_{10 \times 10} &:= 120^2 = 122^2 - 22^2. \end{aligned}$$

ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 12 is forth power of 12, i.e., $T_{12 \times 12} := 12^4$;*

iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4 \times 4} &:= 12^2 \times 4^2 & T_{10 \times 10} &:= 12^2 \times 10^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} &:= 12^2 \times 6^2 & T_{12 \times 12} &:= 12^2 \times 12^2. \\ T_{8 \times 8} &:= 12^2 \times 8^2 \end{aligned}$$

iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{aligned} B_{12 \times 12} &:= T_{12 \times 12} - T_{10 \times 10} = 4 \times (S_{12 \times 12} - S_{10 \times 10}) = 12^2 \times (12^2 - 10^2) = 6336 = 12^2 \times 4 \times 11 \\ B_{10 \times 10} &:= T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 12^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 5184 = 12^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\ B_{8 \times 8} &:= T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 12^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 4032 = 12^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\ B_{6 \times 6} &:= T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 12^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 2880 = 12^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\ B_{4 \times 4} &:= T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 12^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 1728 = 12^2 \times 4 \times 3, \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 137 + 143 + 145 + 151 = 576$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 1152 = 2 \times 4 \times 12^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 576$. This gives $1728 - 576 = 1152$, the same constant value.

2.11 Nested Magic Square of Order 13

Example 2.11. *Let's consider a **nested magic square** of order 13 formed by 169 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 335, 337\}$ given by*

23	1	5	9	13	17	313	309	305	301	297	293	311	2197
335	67	49	53	57	61	269	265	261	257	253	267	3	2197
331	287	231	91	95	99	101	227	223	219	235	51	7	2197
327	283	221	203	123	127	129	199	195	207	117	55	11	2197
323	279	225	197	187	179	149	147	183	141	113	59	15	2197
319	275	229	201	157	163	173	171	181	137	109	63	19	2197
317	273	233	205	153	177	169	161	185	133	105	65	21	2197
31	75	97	125	193	167	165	175	145	213	241	263	307	2197
35	79	93	121	155	159	189	191	151	217	245	259	303	2197
39	83	89	131	215	211	209	139	143	135	249	255	299	2197
43	87	103	247	243	239	237	111	115	119	107	251	295	2197
47	71	289	285	281	277	69	73	77	81	85	271	291	2197
27	337	333	329	325	321	25	29	33	37	41	45	315	2197
2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197	2197

The above *nested magic square* of order 13 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{161, 163, \dots, 175, 177\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{145, 147, \dots, 157, 159, D_{3 \times 3}, 179, 181, \dots, 191, 193\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{121, 123, \dots, 141, 143, D_{5 \times 5}, 195, 197, \dots, 215, 217\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{89, 91, \dots, 117, 119, D_{7 \times 7}, 219, 221, \dots, 247, 249\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{49, 51, \dots, 85, 87, D_{9 \times 9}, 251, 253, \dots, 287, 289\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 45, 47, D_{11 \times 11}, 291, 293, \dots, 335, 337\} \\
 &\dots \tag{14}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 507 & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1521 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 845 & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 1859 \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 1183 & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 2197.
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (14), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 161 + 163 + \dots + 175 + 177 = \left(\frac{177 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{159 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 89^2 - 80^2 = 39^2 = 13^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 145 + 147 + \dots + 191 + 193 = \left(\frac{193 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{143 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 97^2 - 72^2 = 65^2 = 13^2 \times 5^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 121 + 123 + \dots + 215 + 217 = \left(\frac{217+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{119+1}{2}\right)^2 = 109^2 - 60^2 = 91^2 = 13^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 89 + 91 + \dots + 247 + 249 = \left(\frac{249+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{87+1}{2}\right)^2 = 125^2 - 44^2 = 117^2 = 13^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 49 + 51 + \dots + 287 + 289 = \left(\frac{289+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{47+1}{2}\right)^2 = 145^2 - 24^2 = 143^2 = 13^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 335 + 337 = \left(\frac{337+1}{2}\right)^2 = 169^2 = 13^2 \times 13^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.9. *The nested magic square of order 13 formed by 169 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 335, 337\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

- i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 nested in a magic square of order 13 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 39^2 = 89^2 - 80^2 & T_{9 \times 9} &:= 117^2 = 125^2 - 44^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 65^2 = 97^2 - 72^2 & T_{11 \times 11} &:= 143^2 = 145^2 - 24^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 91^2 = 109^2 - 60^2 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

- ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 13 is forth power of 13, i.e., $T_{13 \times 13} := 13^4$;*

- iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 13^2 \times 3^2 & T_{9 \times 9} &:= 13^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 13^2 \times 5^2 & T_{11 \times 11} &:= 13^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 13^2 \times 7^2 & T_{13 \times 13} &:= 13^2 \times 13^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

- iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{13 \times 13} &:= T_{13 \times 13} - T_{11 \times 11} = 4 \times (S_{13 \times 13} - S_{11 \times 11}) = 13^2 \times (13^2 - 11^2) = 8112 = 13^2 \times 2^3 \times 6 \\
 B_{11 \times 11} &:= T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 13^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 6760 = 13^2 \times 2^3 \times 5 \\
 B_{9 \times 9} &:= T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 13^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 5408 = 13^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 13^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 4056 = 13^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 13^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 2704 = 13^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 13^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 1352 = 13^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 169$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 1352$.

2.12 Nested Magic Square of Order 14

Example 2.12. Let's consider a *nested magic square* of order 14 formed by 196 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 389, 391\}$ given by

365	37	357	33	361	29	379	1	369	21	373	17	377	25	2744
351	317	309	311	79	77	63	85	321	323	67	327	73	41	2744
43	87	277	267	127	263	131	123	103	291	99	279	305	349	2744
347	303	121	247	257	137	133	159	235	155	245	271	89	45	2744
47	91	273	241	221	173	227	161	225	169	151	119	301	345	2744
343	299	117	243	215	207	181	187	209	177	149	275	93	49	2744
51	95	287	253	179	193	203	197	191	213	139	105	297	341	2744
39	53	97	153	175	201	195	189	199	217	239	295	339	353	2744
11	61	281	143	163	183	205	211	185	229	249	111	331	381	2744
383	333	109	141	223	219	165	231	167	171	251	283	59	9	2744
7	57	285	147	135	255	259	233	157	237	145	107	335	385	2744
387	337	113	125	265	129	261	269	289	101	293	115	55	5	2744
3	319	83	81	313	315	329	307	71	69	325	65	75	389	2744
367	355	35	359	31	363	13	391	23	371	19	375	15	27	2744

The above *nested magic square* of order 14 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{181, 183, \dots, 209, 211\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{161, 163, \dots, 177, 179, D_{4 \times 4}, 213, 215, \dots, 229, 231\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{133, 135, \dots, 157, 159, D_{6 \times 6}, 233, 235, \dots, 257, 259\} \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{97, 99, \dots, 129, 131, D_{8 \times 8}, 261, 263, \dots, 293, 295\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{53, 55, \dots, 93, 95, D_{10 \times 10}, 297, 299, \dots, 337, 339\} \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 49, 51, D_{12 \times 12}, 341, 343, \dots, 389, 391\} \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 784 & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 1960 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 1176 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 2352 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 1568 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 2744.
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (15), we get

$$T_{4 \times 4} := 181 + 183 + \dots + 209 + 211 = \left(\frac{211 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{179 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 106^2 - 90^2 = 56^2 = 14^2 \times 4^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 161 + 163 + \dots + 229 + 231 = \left(\frac{231+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{159+1}{2}\right)^2 = 116^2 - 80^2 = 84^2 = 14^2 \times 6^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 133 + 135 + \dots + 257 + 259 = \left(\frac{259+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{131+1}{2}\right)^2 = 130^2 - 66^2 = 112^2 = 14^2 \times 8^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 97 + 99 + \dots + 293 + 295 = \left(\frac{295+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{95+1}{2}\right)^2 = 148^2 - 48^2 = 140^2 = 14^2 \times 10^2 \\
 T_{12 \times 12} &:= 53 + 55 + \dots + 337 + 339 = \left(\frac{339+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{51+1}{2}\right)^2 = 170^2 - 26^2 = 168^2 = 14^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{14 \times 14} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 389 + 391 = \left(\frac{391+1}{2}\right)^2 = 196^2 = 14^2 \times 14^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.10. *The nested magic square of order 14 formed by 196 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 389, 391\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 nested in a magic square of order 14 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 56^2 = 106^2 - 90^2 & T_{10 \times 10} &:= 140^2 = 148^2 - 48^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 84^2 = 116^2 - 80^2 & T_{12 \times 12} &:= 168^2 = 170^2 - 26^2. \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 112^2 = 130^2 - 66^2
 \end{aligned}$$

ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 14 is forth power of 14, i.e., $T_{14 \times 14} := 14^4$;*

iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 14^2 \times 4^2 & T_{10 \times 10} &:= 14^2 \times 10^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 14^2 \times 6^2 & T_{12 \times 12} &:= 14^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 14^2 \times 8^2 & T_{14 \times 14} &:= 14^2 \times 14^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{14 \times 14} &:= T_{14 \times 14} - T_{12 \times 12} = 4 \times (S_{14 \times 14} - S_{12 \times 12}) = 14^2 \times (14^2 - 12^2) = 10192 = 14^2 \times 4 \times 13 \\
 B_{12 \times 12} &:= T_{12 \times 12} - T_{10 \times 10} = 4 \times (S_{12 \times 12} - S_{10 \times 10}) = 14^2 \times (12^2 - 10^2) = 8624 = 14^2 \times 4 \times 11 \\
 B_{10 \times 10} &:= T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 14^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 7056 = 14^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\
 B_{8 \times 8} &:= T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 14^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 5488 = 14^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\
 B_{6 \times 6} &:= T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 14^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 3920 = 14^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\
 B_{4 \times 4} &:= T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 14^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 2352 = 14^2 \times 4 \times 3,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 189 + 195 + 197 + 203 = 784$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 1568 = 2 \times 4 \times 14^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 784$. This gives $2352 - 784 = 1568$, the same constant value.

2.13 Nested Magic Square of Order 15

Example 2.13. Let's consider a *nested magic square* of order 15 formed by 225 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 447, 449\}$ given by

															3375
423	395	399	403	407	411	415	25	23	19	15	11	7	3	419	3375
53	79	57	61	65	69	73	369	365	361	357	353	349	367	397	3375
49	391	123	105	109	113	117	325	321	317	313	309	323	59	401	3375
45	387	343	287	147	151	155	157	283	279	275	291	107	63	405	3375
41	383	339	277	259	179	183	185	255	251	263	173	111	67	409	3375
37	379	335	281	253	243	235	205	203	239	197	169	115	71	413	3375
33	375	331	285	257	213	219	229	227	237	193	165	119	75	417	3375
29	373	329	289	261	209	233	225	217	241	189	161	121	77	421	3375
429	87	131	153	181	249	223	221	231	201	269	297	319	363	21	3375
433	91	135	149	177	211	215	245	247	207	273	301	315	359	17	3375
437	95	139	145	187	271	267	265	195	199	191	305	311	355	13	3375
441	99	143	159	303	299	295	293	167	171	175	163	307	351	9	3375
445	103	127	345	341	337	333	125	129	133	137	141	327	347	5	3375
449	83	393	389	385	381	377	81	85	89	93	97	101	371	1	3375
31	55	51	47	43	39	35	425	427	431	435	439	443	447	27	3375
3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375

The above *nested magic square* of order 15 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{217, 219, \dots, 231, 233\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{201, 203, \dots, 213, 215, D_{3 \times 3}, 235, 237, \dots, 247, 249\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{177, 179, \dots, 197, 199, D_{5 \times 5}, 251, 253, \dots, 271, 273\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{145, 147, \dots, 173, 175, D_{7 \times 7}, 275, 277, \dots, 303, 305\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{105, 107, \dots, 141, 143, D_{9 \times 9}, 307, 309, \dots, 343, 345\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{57, 59, \dots, 101, 103, D_{11 \times 11}, 347, 349, \dots, 391, 393\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 53, 55, D_{11 \times 11}, 395, 397, \dots, 447, 449\} \\
 &\dots \tag{16}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 675 & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 2475 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 1125 & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 2925 \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 1575 & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 3375 \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 2025 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (16), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 217 + 219 + \dots + 231 + 233 = \left(\frac{233+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{215+1}{2}\right)^2 = 117^2 - 108^2 = 45^2 = 15^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 201 + 203 + \dots + 247 + 249 = \left(\frac{249+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{199+1}{2}\right)^2 = 125^2 - 100^2 = 75^2 = 15^2 \times 5^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 177 + 179 + \dots + 271 + 273 = \left(\frac{271+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{179+1}{2}\right)^2 = 137^2 - 88^2 = 105^2 = 15^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 145 + 147 + \dots + 303 + 305 = \left(\frac{305+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{143+1}{2}\right)^2 = 153^2 - 72^2 = 135^2 = 15^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 105 + 107 + \dots + 343 + 345 = \left(\frac{345+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{103+1}{2}\right)^2 = 173^2 - 52^2 = 165^2 = 15^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 57 + 59 + \dots + 391 + 393 = \left(\frac{393+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{55+1}{2}\right)^2 = 197^2 - 28^2 = 195^2 = 15^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{15 \times 15} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 447 + 449 = \left(\frac{449+1}{2}\right)^2 = 225^2 = 15^2 \times 15^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.11. *The nested magic square of order 15 formed by 225 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 447, 449\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 nested in a magic square of order 15 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 45^2 = 117^2 - 108^2 & T_{9 \times 9} &:= 135^2 = 153^2 - 72^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 75^2 = 125^2 - 100^2 & T_{11 \times 11} &:= 165^2 = 173^2 - 52^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 105^2 = 137^2 - 88^2 & T_{13 \times 13} &:= 195^2 = 197^2 - 28^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 15 is forth power of 15, i.e., $T_{15 \times 15} := 15^4$;*

iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 15^2 \times 3^2 & T_{11 \times 11} &:= 15^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 15^2 \times 5^2 & T_{13 \times 13} &:= 15^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 15^2 \times 7^2 & T_{15 \times 15} &:= 15^2 \times 15^2. \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 15^2 \times 9^2 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{15 \times 15} &:= T_{15 \times 15} - T_{13 \times 13} = 4 \times (S_{15 \times 15} - S_{13 \times 13}) = 15^2 \times (15^2 - 13^2) = 12600 = 15^2 \times 2^3 \times 7 \\
 B_{13 \times 13} &:= T_{13 \times 13} - T_{11 \times 11} = 4 \times (S_{11 \times 11} - S_{9 \times 9}) = 15^2 \times (13^2 - 11^2) = 10800 = 15^2 \times 2^3 \times 6 \\
 B_{11 \times 11} &:= T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 15^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 9000 = 15^2 \times 2^3 \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{9 \times 9} &:= T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} &= 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) &= 15^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) &= 7200 &= 15^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} &= 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) &= 15^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) &= 5400 &= 15^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} &= 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) &= 15^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) &= 3600 &= 15^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} &= 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) &= 15^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) &= 1800 &= 15^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 225$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 1800$.

2.14 Nested Magic Square of Order 16

Example 2.14. Let's consider a nested magic square of order 16 formed by 256 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 509, 511\}$ given by

481	469	41	473	475	35	33	15	45	485	487	23	491	19	495	29	4096
47	425	97	417	93	421	89	439	61	429	81	433	77	437	85	465	4096
463	411	377	369	371	139	137	123	145	381	383	127	387	133	101	49	4096
51	103	147	337	327	187	323	191	183	163	351	159	339	365	409	461	4096
459	407	363	181	307	317	197	193	219	295	215	305	331	149	105	53	4096
55	107	151	333	301	281	233	287	221	285	229	211	179	361	405	457	4096
455	403	359	177	303	275	267	241	247	269	237	209	335	153	109	57	4096
59	111	155	347	313	239	253	263	257	251	273	199	165	357	401	453	4096
1	99	113	157	213	235	261	255	249	259	277	299	355	399	413	511	4096
13	71	121	341	203	223	243	265	271	245	289	309	171	391	441	499	4096
501	443	393	169	201	283	279	225	291	227	231	311	343	119	69	11	4096
9	67	117	345	207	195	315	319	293	217	297	205	167	395	445	503	4096
505	447	397	173	185	325	189	321	329	349	161	353	175	115	65	7	4096
5	63	379	143	141	373	375	389	367	131	129	385	125	135	449	507	4096
509	427	415	95	419	91	423	73	451	83	431	79	435	75	87	3	4096
483	43	471	39	37	477	479	497	467	27	25	489	21	493	17	31	4096
4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096

The above nested magic square of order 16 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{241, 243, \dots, 269, 271\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{221, 223, \dots, 237, 239, D_{4 \times 4}, 273, 275, \dots, 289, 291\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{193, 195, \dots, 217, 219, D_{6 \times 6}, 293, 295, \dots, 317, 319\} \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{157, 159, \dots, 189, 191, D_{8 \times 8}, 321, 323, \dots, 353, 355\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{113, 115, \dots, 153, 155, D_{10 \times 10}, 357, 359, \dots, 397, 399\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{61, 63, \dots, 109, 111, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 401, 403, \dots, 449, 451\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 57, 59, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 453, 455, \dots, 509, 511\} \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 1024 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 3072 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 1536 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 3584 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 2048 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 4096. \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= 2560
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (17), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 241 + 243 + \dots + 269 + 271 = \left(\frac{271+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{239+1}{2}\right)^2 = 136^2 - 120^2 = 64^2 = 16^2 \times 4^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 221 + 223 + \dots + 289 + 291 = \left(\frac{291+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{219+1}{2}\right)^2 = 146^2 - 110^2 = 96^2 = 16^2 \times 6^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 193 + 195 + \dots + 317 + 319 = \left(\frac{319+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{191+1}{2}\right)^2 = 160^2 - 96^2 = 128^2 = 16^2 \times 8^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 157 + 159 + \dots + 353 + 355 = \left(\frac{355+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{155+1}{2}\right)^2 = 178^2 - 78^2 = 160^2 = 16^2 \times 10^2 \\
 T_{12 \times 12} &:= 113 + 115 + \dots + 397 + 399 = \left(\frac{399+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{111+1}{2}\right)^2 = 200^2 - 56^2 = 192^2 = 16^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{14 \times 14} &:= 61 + 63 + \dots + 449 + 451 = \left(\frac{451+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{59+1}{2}\right)^2 = 226^2 - 30^2 = 224^2 = 16^2 \times 14^2 \\
 T_{16 \times 16} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 509 + 511 = \left(\frac{511+1}{2}\right)^2 = 256^2 = 16^2 \times 16^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.12. The nested magic square of order 16 formed by 256 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 509, 511\}$ satisfy the following properties:

i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 nested in a magic square of order 16 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 64^2 = 136^2 - 120^2 & T_{10 \times 10} &:= 160^2 = 178^2 - 78^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 96^2 = 146^2 - 110^2 & T_{12 \times 12} &:= 192^2 = 200^2 - 56^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 128^2 = 160^2 - 96^2 & T_{14 \times 14} &:= 224^2 = 226^2 - 30^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 16 is forth power of 16, i.e., $T_{16 \times 16} := 16^4$;

iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 16^2 \times 4^2 & T_{12 \times 12} &:= 16^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 16^2 \times 6^2 & T_{14 \times 14} &:= 16^2 \times 14^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 16^2 \times 8^2 & T_{16 \times 16} &:= 16^2 \times 16^2. \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 16^2 \times 10^2
 \end{aligned}$$

iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{16 \times 16} &:= T_{16 \times 16} - T_{14 \times 14} = 4 \times (S_{16 \times 16} - S_{14 \times 14}) = 16^2 \times (16^2 - 14^2) = 15360 = 16^2 \times 4 \times 15 \\
 B_{14 \times 14} &:= T_{14 \times 14} - T_{12 \times 12} = 4 \times (S_{14 \times 14} - S_{12 \times 12}) = 16^2 \times (14^2 - 12^2) = 13312 = 16^2 \times 4 \times 13 \\
 B_{12 \times 12} &:= T_{12 \times 12} - T_{10 \times 10} = 4 \times (S_{12 \times 12} - S_{10 \times 10}) = 16^2 \times (12^2 - 10^2) = 11264 = 16^2 \times 4 \times 11 \\
 B_{10 \times 10} &:= T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 16^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 9216 = 16^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\
 B_{8 \times 8} &:= T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 16^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 7168 = 16^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\
 B_{6 \times 6} &:= T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 16^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 5120 = 16^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\
 B_{4 \times 4} &:= T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 16^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 3072 = 16^2 \times 4 \times 3,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 249 + 255 + 257 + 263 = 1024$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 2048 = 2 \times 4 \times 16^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e, $T_{2 \times 2} := 1024$. This gives $3072 - 1024 = 2048$, the same constant value.

2.15 Nested Magic Square of Order 17

Example 2.15. Let's consider a **nested magic square** of order 17 formed by 289 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 575, 577\}$ given by

547	61	57	53	49	45	41	37	33	553	557	561	565	569	573	577	35	4913
515	487	459	463	467	471	475	479	89	87	83	79	75	71	67	483	63	4913
519	117	143	121	125	129	133	137	433	429	425	421	417	413	431	461	59	4913
523	113	455	187	169	173	177	181	389	385	381	377	373	387	123	465	55	4913
527	109	451	407	351	211	215	219	221	347	343	339	355	171	127	469	51	4913
531	105	447	403	341	323	243	247	249	319	315	327	237	175	131	473	47	4913
535	101	443	399	345	317	307	299	269	267	303	261	233	179	135	477	43	4913
539	97	439	395	349	321	277	283	293	291	301	257	229	183	139	481	39	4913
29	93	437	393	353	325	273	297	289	281	305	253	225	185	141	485	549	4913
27	493	151	195	217	245	313	287	285	295	265	333	361	383	427	85	551	4913
23	497	155	199	213	241	275	279	309	311	271	337	365	379	423	81	555	4913
19	501	159	203	209	251	335	331	329	259	263	255	369	375	419	77	559	4913
15	505	163	207	223	367	363	359	357	231	235	239	227	371	415	73	563	4913
11	509	167	191	409	405	401	397	189	193	197	201	205	391	411	69	567	4913
7	513	147	457	453	449	445	441	145	149	153	157	161	165	435	65	571	4913
3	95	119	115	111	107	103	99	489	491	495	499	503	507	511	91	575	4913
543	517	521	525	529	533	537	541	545	25	21	17	13	9	5	1	31	4913

4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913 4913

The above nested magic square of order 17 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{281, 283, \dots, 295, 297\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{265, 267, \dots, 277, 279, D_{3 \times 3}, 299, 301, \dots, 311, 313\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{241, 243, \dots, 261, 263, D_{5 \times 5}, 315, 317, \dots, 335, 337\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{209, 211, \dots, 237, 239, D_{7 \times 7}, 339, 341, \dots, 367, 369\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{169, 171, \dots, 205, 207, D_{9 \times 9}, 371, 373, \dots, 407, 409\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{121, 123, \dots, 165, 167, D_{11 \times 11}, 411, 413, \dots, 455, 457\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{65, 67, \dots, 117, 119, D_{13 \times 13}, 459, 461, \dots, 511, 513\} \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 61, 63, D_{15 \times 15}, 515, 517, \dots, 575, 577\} \\
 &\dots \tag{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 867 & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 3179 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 1445 & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 3757 \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 2023 & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 4335 \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 2601 & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 4913
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (18), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 281 + 283 + \dots + 295 + 297 = \left(\frac{297+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{279+1}{2}\right)^2 = 149^2 - 140^2 = 51^2 = 17^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 265 + 267 + \dots + 311 + 313 = \left(\frac{313+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{263+1}{2}\right)^2 = 157^2 - 132^2 = 85^2 = 17^2 \times 5^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 241 + 243 + \dots + 335 + 337 = \left(\frac{337+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{239+1}{2}\right)^2 = 160^2 - 120^2 = 119^2 = 17^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 209 + 211 + \dots + 367 + 369 = \left(\frac{369+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{207+1}{2}\right)^2 = 185^2 - 104^2 = 153^2 = 17^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 169 + 171 + \dots + 407 + 409 = \left(\frac{409+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{167+1}{2}\right)^2 = 205^2 - 84^2 = 187^2 = 17^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 121 + 123 + \dots + 455 + 457 = \left(\frac{457+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{119+1}{2}\right)^2 = 229^2 - 60^2 = 221^2 = 17^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{15 \times 15} &:= 65 + 67 + \dots + 511 + 513 = \left(\frac{513+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{63+1}{2}\right)^2 = 257^2 - 32^2 = 255^2 = 17^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{17 \times 17} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 575 + 577 = \left(\frac{577+1}{2}\right)^2 = 289^2 = 17^2 \times 17^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.13. *The nested magic square of order 17 formed by 289 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 575, 577\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

- i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 and 15 nested in a magic square of order 17 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 51^2 = 149^2 - 140^2 & T_{11 \times 11} &:= 187^2 = 205^2 - 84^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 85^2 = 157^2 - 132^2 & T_{13 \times 13} &:= 221^2 = 229^2 - 60^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 119^2 = 160^2 - 120^2 & T_{15 \times 15} &:= 255^2 = 257^2 - 32^2. \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 153^2 = 185^2 - 104^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 17 is forth power of 17, i.e., $T_{17 \times 17} := 17^4$;*

- iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 17^2 \times 3^2 & T_{11 \times 11} &:= 17^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 17^2 \times 5^2 & T_{13 \times 13} &:= 17^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 17^2 \times 7^2 & T_{15 \times 15} &:= 17^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 17^2 \times 9^2 & T_{17 \times 17} &:= 17^2 \times 17^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{17 \times 17} &:= T_{17 \times 17} - T_{15 \times 15} = 4 \times (S_{17 \times 17} - S_{15 \times 15}) = 17^2 \times (17^2 - 15^2) = 18496 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 8 \\
 B_{15 \times 15} &:= T_{15 \times 15} - T_{13 \times 13} = 4 \times (S_{15 \times 15} - S_{13 \times 13}) = 17^2 \times (15^2 - 13^2) = 16184 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 7 \\
 B_{13 \times 13} &:= T_{13 \times 13} - T_{11 \times 11} = 4 \times (S_{11 \times 11} - S_{9 \times 9}) = 17^2 \times (13^2 - 11^2) = 13872 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 6 \\
 B_{11 \times 11} &:= T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 17^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 11560 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 5 \\
 B_{9 \times 9} &:= T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 17^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 9248 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 17^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 6936 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 17^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 4624 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 17^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 2312 = 17^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 17^2 = 289$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 2312 = 17^2 \times 8$.

2.16 Nested Magic Square of Order 18

Example 2.16. Let's consider a nested magic square of order 18 formed by 324 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 645, 647\}$ given by

613	49	601	45	605	41	609	37	631	1	617	29	621	25	625	21	629	33	5832	
595	549	537	109	541	543	103	101	83	113	553	555	91	559	87	563	97	53	5832	
55	115	493	165	485	161	489	157	507	129	497	149	501	145	505	153	533	593	5832	
591	531	479	445	437	439	207	205	191	213	449	451	195	455	201	169	117	57	5832	
59	119	171	215	405	395	255	391	259	251	231	419	227	407	433	477	529	589	5832	
587	527	475	431	249	375	385	265	261	287	363	283	373	399	217	173	121	61	5832	
63	123	175	219	401	369	349	301	355	289	353	297	279	247	429	473	525	585	5832	
583	523	471	427	245	371	343	335	309	315	337	305	277	403	221	177	125	65	5832	
67	127	179	223	415	381	307	321	331	325	319	341	267	233	425	469	521	581	5832	
51	69	167	181	225	281	303	329	323	317	327	345	367	423	467	481	579	597	5832	
15	81	139	189	409	271	291	311	333	339	313	357	377	239	459	509	567	633	5832	
635	569	511	461	237	269	351	347	293	359	295	299	379	411	187	137	79	13	5832	
11	77	135	185	413	275	263	383	387	361	285	365	273	235	463	513	571	637	5832	
639	573	515	465	241	253	393	257	389	397	417	229	421	243	183	133	75	9	5832	
7	73	131	447	211	209	441	443	457	435	199	197	453	193	203	517	575	641	5832	
643	577	495	483	163	487	159	491	141	519	151	499	147	503	143	155	71	5	5832	
3	551	111	539	107	105	545	547	565	535	95	93	557	89	561	85	99	645	5832	
615	599	47	603	43	607	39	611	17	647	31	619	27	623	23	627	19	35	5832	
5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832

The above *nested magic square* of order 18 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{309, 311, \dots, 337, 339\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{289, 291, \dots, 305, 307, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 341, 343, \dots, 357, 359\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{261, 263, \dots, 285, 287, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 361, 363, \dots, 385, 387\} \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{225, 227, \dots, 257, 259, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 389, 391, \dots, 421, 423\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{181, 183, \dots, 221, 223, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 425, 427, \dots, 465, 467\} \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{129, 131, \dots, 177, 179, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 469, 471, \dots, 517, 519\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{69, 71, \dots, 125, 127, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 521, 523, \dots, 577, 579\} \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 65, 67, \mathbf{D}_{16 \times 16}, 581, 583, \dots, 645, 647\} \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 1296 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 3888 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 1944 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 4536 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 2592 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 5184 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= 3240 & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 5832.
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (19), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 309 + 311 + \dots + 337 + 339 = \left(\frac{339 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{307 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 170^2 - 154^2 = 72^2 = 18^2 \times 4^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 289 + 291 + \dots + 357 + 359 = \left(\frac{359 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{287 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 180^2 - 144^2 = 108^2 = 18^2 \times 6^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 261 + 263 + \dots + 385 + 387 = \left(\frac{387 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{259 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 194^2 - 130^2 = 144^2 = 18^2 \times 8^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 225 + 227 + \dots + 421 + 423 = \left(\frac{423 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{223 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 212^2 - 112^2 = 180^2 = 18^2 \times 10^2 \\
 T_{12 \times 12} &:= 181 + 183 + \dots + 465 + 467 = \left(\frac{467 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{179 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 234^2 - 90^2 = 216^2 = 18^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{14 \times 14} &:= 129 + 131 + \dots + 517 + 519 = \left(\frac{519 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{127 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 260^2 - 64^2 = 252^2 = 18^2 \times 14^2 \\
 T_{16 \times 16} &:= 67 + 69 + \dots + 577 + 579 = \left(\frac{579 + 1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{67 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 290^2 - 34^2 = 288^2 = 18^2 \times 16^2 \\
 T_{18 \times 18} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 645 + 647 = \left(\frac{647 + 1}{2}\right)^2 = 324^2 = 18^2 \times 18^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.14. The nested magic square of order 18 formed by 324 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 645, 647\}$ satisfy the following properties:

i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16 nested in a magic square of order 18 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4 \times 4} &:= 72^2 = 170^2 - 154^2 & T_{12 \times 12} &:= 216^2 = 234^2 - 90^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} &:= 108^2 = 180^2 - 144^2 & T_{14 \times 14} &:= 252^2 = 260^2 - 64^2 \\ T_{8 \times 8} &:= 144^2 = 194^2 - 130^2 & T_{16 \times 16} &:= 288^2 = 290^2 - 34^2. \\ T_{10 \times 10} &:= 180^2 = 212^2 - 112^2 \end{aligned}$$

ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 18 is forth power of 18, i.e., $T_{18 \times 18} := 18^4$;

iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4 \times 4} &:= 18^2 \times 4^2 & T_{12 \times 12} &:= 18^2 \times 12^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} &:= 18^2 \times 6^2 & T_{14 \times 14} &:= 18^2 \times 14^2 \\ T_{8 \times 8} &:= 18^2 \times 8^2 & T_{16 \times 16} &:= 18^2 \times 16^2 \\ T_{10 \times 10} &:= 18^2 \times 10^2 & T_{18 \times 18} &:= 18^2 \times 18^2. \end{aligned}$$

iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned} B_{18 \times 18} &:= T_{18 \times 18} - T_{16 \times 16} = 4 \times (S_{18 \times 18} - S_{16 \times 16}) = 18^2 \times (18^2 - 16^2) = 22032 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 17 \\ B_{16 \times 16} &:= T_{16 \times 16} - T_{14 \times 14} = 4 \times (S_{16 \times 16} - S_{14 \times 14}) = 18^2 \times (16^2 - 14^2) = 19440 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 15 \\ B_{14 \times 14} &:= T_{14 \times 14} - T_{12 \times 12} = 4 \times (S_{14 \times 14} - S_{12 \times 12}) = 18^2 \times (14^2 - 12^2) = 16848 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 13 \\ B_{12 \times 12} &:= T_{12 \times 12} - T_{10 \times 10} = 4 \times (S_{12 \times 12} - S_{10 \times 10}) = 18^2 \times (12^2 - 10^2) = 14256 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 11 \\ B_{10 \times 10} &:= T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 18^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 11664 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\ B_{8 \times 8} &:= T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 18^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 9072 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\ B_{6 \times 6} &:= T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 18^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 6480 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\ B_{4 \times 4} &:= T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 18^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 3888 = 18^2 \times 4 \times 3, \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 317 + 323 + 325 + 331 = 1296$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 2592 = 2 \times 4 \times 18^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 1296$. This gives $3888 - 1296 = 2592$, the same constant value.

2.17 Nested Magic Square of Order 19

Example 2.17. Let's consider a **nested magic square** of order 19 formed by 361 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 719, 721\}$ given by

687	69	65	61	57	53	49	45	41	37	693	697	701	705	709	713	717	721	39	6859
651	619	133	129	125	121	117	113	109	105	625	629	633	637	641	645	649	107	71	6859
655	587	559	531	535	539	543	547	551	161	159	155	151	147	143	139	555	135	67	6859
659	591	189	215	193	197	201	205	209	505	501	497	493	489	485	503	533	131	63	6859
663	595	185	527	259	241	245	249	253	461	457	453	449	445	459	195	537	127	59	6859
667	599	181	523	479	423	283	287	291	293	419	415	411	427	243	199	541	123	55	6859
671	603	177	519	475	413	395	315	319	321	391	387	399	309	247	203	545	119	51	6859
675	607	173	515	471	417	389	379	371	341	339	375	333	305	251	207	549	115	47	6859
679	611	169	511	467	421	393	349	355	365	363	373	329	301	255	211	553	111	43	6859
33	101	165	509	465	425	397	345	369	361	353	377	325	297	257	213	557	621	689	6859
31	99	565	223	267	289	317	385	359	357	367	337	405	433	455	499	157	623	691	6859
27	95	569	227	271	285	313	347	351	381	383	343	409	437	451	495	153	627	695	6859
23	91	573	231	275	281	323	407	403	401	331	335	327	441	447	491	149	631	699	6859
19	87	577	235	279	295	439	435	431	429	303	307	311	299	443	487	145	635	703	6859
15	83	581	239	263	481	477	473	469	261	265	269	273	277	463	483	141	639	707	6859
11	79	585	219	529	525	521	517	513	217	221	225	229	233	237	507	137	643	711	6859
7	75	167	191	187	183	179	175	171	561	563	567	571	575	579	583	163	647	715	6859
3	615	589	593	597	601	605	609	613	617	97	93	89	85	81	77	73	103	719	6859
683	653	657	661	665	669	673	677	681	685	29	25	21	17	13	9	5	1	35	6859

The above *nested magic square* of order 19 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{353, 355, \dots, 367, 369\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{337, 339, \dots, 349, 351, D_{3 \times 3}, 371, 373, \dots, 383, 385\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{313, 315, \dots, 333, 335, D_{5 \times 5}, 387, 389, \dots, 407, 409\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{281, 283, \dots, 309, 311, D_{7 \times 7}, 411, 413, \dots, 439, 441\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{241, 243, \dots, 277, 279, D_{9 \times 9}, 443, 445, \dots, 479, 481\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{193, 195, \dots, 237, 239, D_{11 \times 11}, 483, 485, \dots, 527, 529\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{137, 139, \dots, 189, 191, D_{13 \times 13}, 531, 533, \dots, 583, 585\} \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{73, 75, \dots, 133, 135, D_{15 \times 15}, 587, 589, \dots, 647, 649\} \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 69, 71, D_{17 \times 17}, 651, 653, \dots, 719, 721\}
 \end{aligned}$$

... (20)

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{3 \times 3} := 1083 & S_{13 \times 13} := 4693 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} := 1805 & S_{15 \times 15} := 5415 \\
 S_{7 \times 7} := 2527 & S_{17 \times 17} := 6137 \\
 S_{9 \times 9} := 3249 & S_{19 \times 19} := 6859. \\
 S_{11 \times 11} := 3971 &
 \end{array}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (20), we get

$$\begin{array}{l}
 T_{3 \times 3} := 353 + 355 + \dots + 367 + 369 = \left(\frac{369+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{351+1}{2}\right)^2 = 185^2 - 176^2 = 57^2 = 19^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} := 337 + 339 + \dots + 383 + 385 = \left(\frac{385+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{335+1}{2}\right)^2 = 193^2 - 168^2 = 95^2 = 19^2 \times 5^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} := 313 + 315 + \dots + 407 + 409 = \left(\frac{409+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{311+1}{2}\right)^2 = 205^2 - 156^2 = 133^2 = 19^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} := 281 + 283 + \dots + 439 + 441 = \left(\frac{441+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{279+1}{2}\right)^2 = 221^2 - 140^2 = 171^2 = 19^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} := 241 + 243 + \dots + 479 + 481 = \left(\frac{481+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{239+1}{2}\right)^2 = 241^2 - 120^2 = 209^2 = 19^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} := 193 + 195 + \dots + 527 + 529 = \left(\frac{529+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{191+1}{2}\right)^2 = 265^2 - 96^2 = 247^2 = 19^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{15 \times 15} := 137 + 139 + \dots + 583 + 585 = \left(\frac{585+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{135+1}{2}\right)^2 = 293^2 - 68^2 = 285^2 = 19^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{17 \times 17} := 73 + 75 + \dots + 647 + 649 = \left(\frac{649+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{71+1}{2}\right)^2 = 325^2 - 36^2 = 323^2 = 19^2 \times 17^2 \\
 T_{19 \times 19} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 719 + 721 = \left(\frac{721+1}{2}\right)^2 = 361^2 = 19^2 \times 19^2.
 \end{array}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.15. *The nested magic square of order 19 formed by 324 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 719, 721\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

- i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15 and 17 nested in a magic square of order 19 satisfy Pythagorean triple property, i.e.,*

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 T_{3 \times 3} := 57^2 = 185^2 - 176^2 & T_{11 \times 11} := 209^2 = 241^2 - 120^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} := 95^2 = 193^2 - 168^2 & T_{13 \times 13} := 247^2 = 265^2 - 96^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} := 133^2 = 205^2 - 156^2 & T_{15 \times 15} := 285^2 = 293^2 - 68^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} := 171^2 = 221^2 - 140^2 & T_{17 \times 17} := 323^2 = 325^2 - 36^2.
 \end{array}$$

ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 19 is forth power of 19, i.e., $T_{19 \times 19} := 19^4$;

iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 T_{3 \times 3} := 19^2 \times 3^2 & T_{13 \times 13} := 19^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} := 19^2 \times 5^2 & T_{15 \times 15} := 19^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} := 19^2 \times 7^2 & T_{17 \times 17} := 19^2 \times 17^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} := 19^2 \times 9^2 & T_{19 \times 19} := 19^2 \times 19^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} := 19^2 \times 11^2 &
 \end{array}$$

iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{array}{l}
 B_{19 \times 19} := T_{19 \times 19} - T_{17 \times 17} = 4 \times (S_{19 \times 19} - S_{17 \times 17}) = 19^2 \times (19^2 - 17^2) = 25992 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 9 \\
 B_{17 \times 17} := T_{17 \times 17} - T_{15 \times 15} = 4 \times (S_{17 \times 17} - S_{15 \times 15}) = 19^2 \times (17^2 - 15^2) = 23104 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 8 \\
 B_{15 \times 15} := T_{15 \times 15} - T_{13 \times 13} = 4 \times (S_{15 \times 15} - S_{13 \times 13}) = 19^2 \times (15^2 - 13^2) = 20216 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 7 \\
 B_{13 \times 13} := T_{13 \times 13} - T_{11 \times 11} = 4 \times (S_{11 \times 11} - S_{9 \times 9}) = 19^2 \times (13^2 - 11^2) = 17328 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 6 \\
 B_{11 \times 11} := T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 19^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 14440 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 5 \\
 B_{9 \times 9} := T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 19^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 11552 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} := T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 19^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 8664 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} := T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 19^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 5776 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} := T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 19^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 2888 = 19^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{array}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 19^2 = 361$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 2888 = 19^2 \times 8$.

2.18 Nested Magic Square of Order 20

Example 2.18. Let's consider a nested magic square of order 20 formed by 400 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 797, 799\}$ given by

761	745	53	749	49	753	755	43	41	19	57	765	767	31	771	27	775	23	779	37	8000
59	689	125	677	121	681	117	685	113	707	77	693	105	697	101	701	97	705	109	741	8000
739	671	625	613	185	617	619	179	177	159	189	629	631	167	635	163	639	173	129	61	8000
63	131	191	569	241	561	237	565	233	583	205	573	225	577	221	581	229	609	669	737	8000
735	667	607	555	521	513	515	283	281	267	289	525	527	271	531	277	245	193	133	65	8000
67	135	195	247	291	481	471	331	467	335	327	307	495	303	483	509	553	605	665	733	8000
731	663	603	551	507	325	451	461	341	337	363	439	359	449	475	293	249	197	137	69	8000
71	139	199	251	295	477	445	425	377	431	365	429	373	355	323	505	549	601	661	729	8000
727	659	599	547	503	321	447	419	411	385	391	413	381	353	479	297	253	201	141	73	8000
75	143	203	255	299	491	457	383	397	407	401	395	417	343	309	501	545	597	657	725	8000
1	127	145	243	257	301	357	379	405	399	393	403	421	443	499	543	557	655	673	799	8000
17	91	157	215	265	485	347	367	387	409	415	389	433	453	315	535	585	643	709	783	8000
785	711	645	587	537	313	345	427	423	369	435	371	375	455	487	263	213	155	89	15	8000
13	87	153	211	261	489	351	339	459	463	437	361	441	349	311	539	589	647	713	787	8000
789	715	649	591	541	317	329	469	333	465	473	493	305	497	319	259	209	151	85	11	8000
9	83	149	207	523	287	285	517	519	533	511	275	273	529	269	279	593	651	717	791	8000
793	719	653	571	559	239	563	235	567	217	595	227	575	223	579	219	231	147	81	7	8000
5	79	627	187	615	183	181	621	623	641	611	171	169	633	165	637	161	175	721	795	8000
797	691	675	123	679	119	683	115	687	93	723	107	695	103	699	99	703	95	111	3	8000
763	55	747	51	751	47	45	757	759	781	743	35	33	769	29	773	25	777	21	39	8000

The above *nested magic square* of order 20 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{385, 387, \dots, 413, 415\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{365, 367, \dots, 381, 383, D_{4 \times 4}, 417, 419, \dots, 433, 435\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{337, 339, \dots, 361, 363, D_{6 \times 6}, 437, 439, \dots, 461, 463\} \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{301, 303, \dots, 333, 335, D_{8 \times 8}, 465, 467, \dots, 497, 499\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{257, 259, \dots, 297, 299, D_{10 \times 10}, 501, 503, \dots, 541, 543\} \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{205, 207, \dots, 253, 255, D_{12 \times 12}, 545, 547, \dots, 593, 595\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{145, 147, \dots, 201, 203, D_{14 \times 14}, 597, 599, \dots, 653, 655\} \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{77, 79, \dots, 141, 143, D_{16 \times 16}, 657, 659, \dots, 721, 723\} \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 81, 83, D_{18 \times 18}, 581, 583, \dots, 797, 799\}
 \end{aligned}$$

... (21)

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{4 \times 4} := 1600 & S_{14 \times 14} := 5600 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} := 2400 & S_{16 \times 16} := 6400 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} := 3200 & S_{18 \times 18} := 7200 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} := 4000 & S_{20 \times 20} := 8000. \\
 S_{12 \times 12} := 4800 &
 \end{array}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (21), we get

$$\begin{array}{l}
 T_{4 \times 4} := 385 + 387 + \dots + 413 + 415 = \left(\frac{415+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{383+1}{2}\right)^2 = 208^2 - 192^2 = 80^2 = 20^2 \times 4^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} := 365 + 367 + \dots + 433 + 435 = \left(\frac{435+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{363+1}{2}\right)^2 = 218^2 - 182^2 = 120^2 = 20^2 \times 6^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} := 337 + 339 + \dots + 461 + 463 = \left(\frac{463+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{335+1}{2}\right)^2 = 232^2 - 168^2 = 160^2 = 20^2 \times 8^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} := 301 + 303 + \dots + 497 + 499 = \left(\frac{499+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{299+1}{2}\right)^2 = 250^2 - 150^2 = 200^2 = 20^2 \times 10^2 \\
 T_{12 \times 12} := 257 + 259 + \dots + 541 + 543 = \left(\frac{543+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{255+1}{2}\right)^2 = 272^2 - 128^2 = 240^2 = 20^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{14 \times 14} := 205 + 207 + \dots + 593 + 595 = \left(\frac{595+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{203+1}{2}\right)^2 = 298^2 - 102^2 = 280^2 = 20^2 \times 14^2 \\
 T_{16 \times 16} := 145 + 147 + \dots + 653 + 655 = \left(\frac{655+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{143+1}{2}\right)^2 = 328^2 - 72^2 = 320^2 = 20^2 \times 16^2 \\
 T_{18 \times 18} := 77 + 79 + \dots + 721 + 723 = \left(\frac{723+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{75+1}{2}\right)^2 = 362^2 - 38^2 = 360^2 = 20^2 \times 18^2 \\
 T_{20 \times 20} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 797 + 799 = \left(\frac{799+1}{2}\right)^2 = 400^2 = 20^2 \times 20^2.
 \end{array}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.16. *The nested magic square of order 20 formed by 400 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 797, 799\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 and 18 nested in a magic square of order 20 satisfy Pythagorean triple property, i.e.,

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 T_{4 \times 4} := 80^2 = 208^2 - 192^2 & T_{12 \times 12} := 240^2 = 272^2 - 128^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} := 120^2 = 218^2 - 182^2 & T_{14 \times 14} := 280^2 = 298^2 - 102^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} := 160^2 = 232^2 - 168^2 & T_{16 \times 16} := 320^2 = 328^2 - 72^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} := 200^2 = 250^2 - 150^2 & T_{18 \times 18} := 360^2 = 362^2 - 38^2.
 \end{array}$$

ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 20 is forth power of 20, i.e., $T_{20 \times 20} := 20^4$;

iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 T_{4 \times 4} := 20^2 \times 4^2 & T_{12 \times 12} := 20^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} := 20^2 \times 6^2 & T_{14 \times 14} := 20^2 \times 14^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} := 20^2 \times 8^2 & T_{16 \times 16} := 20^2 \times 16^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} := 20^2 \times 10^2 & T_{18 \times 18} := 20^2 \times 18^2 \\
 & T_{20 \times 20} := 20^2 \times 20^2.
 \end{array}$$

iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{array}{l}
 B_{20 \times 20} := T_{20 \times 20} - T_{18 \times 18} = 4 \times (S_{20 \times 20} - S_{18 \times 18}) = 20^2 \times (20^2 - 18^2) = 30400 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 19 \\
 B_{18 \times 18} := T_{18 \times 18} - T_{16 \times 16} = 4 \times (S_{18 \times 18} - S_{16 \times 16}) = 20^2 \times (18^2 - 16^2) = 27200 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 17 \\
 B_{16 \times 16} := T_{16 \times 16} - T_{14 \times 14} = 4 \times (S_{16 \times 16} - S_{14 \times 14}) = 20^2 \times (16^2 - 14^2) = 24000 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 15 \\
 B_{14 \times 14} := T_{14 \times 14} - T_{12 \times 12} = 4 \times (S_{14 \times 14} - S_{12 \times 12}) = 20^2 \times (14^2 - 12^2) = 20800 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 13 \\
 B_{12 \times 12} := T_{12 \times 12} - T_{10 \times 10} = 4 \times (S_{12 \times 12} - S_{10 \times 10}) = 20^2 \times (12^2 - 10^2) = 17600 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 11 \\
 B_{10 \times 10} := T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 20^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 14400 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\
 B_{8 \times 8} := T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 20^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 11200 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\
 B_{6 \times 6} := T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 20^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 8000 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\
 B_{4 \times 4} := T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 20^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 4800 = 20^2 \times 4 \times 3
 \end{array}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 393 + 399 + 401 + 407 = 1600$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 3200 = 2 \times 4 \times 20^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 1600$. This gives $4800 - 1600 = 3200$, the same constant value.

2.19 Nested Magic Square of Order 21

Example 2.19. Let's consider a **nested magic square** of order 21 formed by 441 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 879, 881\}$ given by

839	805	809	813	817	821	825	829	833	837	841	33	29	25	21	17	13	9	5	1	39	9261
3	767	149	145	141	137	133	129	125	121	117	773	777	781	785	789	793	797	801	119	879	9261
7	731	699	213	209	205	201	197	193	189	185	705	709	713	717	721	725	729	187	151	875	9261
11	735	667	639	611	615	619	623	627	631	241	239	235	231	227	223	219	635	215	147	871	9261
15	739	671	269	295	273	277	281	285	289	585	581	577	573	569	565	583	613	211	143	867	9261
19	743	675	265	607	339	321	325	329	333	541	537	533	529	525	539	275	617	207	139	863	9261
23	747	679	261	603	559	503	363	367	371	373	499	495	491	507	323	279	621	203	135	859	9261
27	751	683	257	599	555	493	475	395	399	401	471	467	479	389	327	283	625	199	131	855	9261
31	755	687	253	595	551	497	469	459	451	421	419	455	413	385	331	287	629	195	127	851	9261
35	759	691	249	591	547	501	473	429	435	445	443	453	409	381	335	291	633	191	123	847	9261
37	113	181	245	589	545	505	477	425	449	441	433	457	405	377	337	293	637	701	769	845	9261
835	111	179	645	303	347	369	397	465	439	437	447	417	485	513	535	579	237	703	771	47	9261
831	107	175	649	307	351	365	393	427	431	461	463	423	489	517	531	575	233	707	775	51	9261
827	103	171	653	311	355	361	403	487	483	481	411	415	407	521	527	571	229	711	779	55	9261
823	99	167	657	315	359	375	519	515	511	509	383	387	391	379	523	567	225	715	783	59	9261
819	95	163	661	319	343	561	557	553	549	341	345	349	353	357	543	563	221	719	787	63	9261
815	91	159	665	299	609	605	601	597	593	297	301	305	309	313	317	587	217	723	791	67	9261
811	87	155	247	271	267	263	259	255	251	641	643	647	651	655	659	663	243	727	795	71	9261
807	83	695	669	673	677	681	685	689	693	697	177	173	169	165	161	157	153	183	799	75	9261
803	763	733	737	741	745	749	753	757	761	765	109	105	101	97	93	89	85	81	115	79	9261
843	77	73	69	65	61	57	53	49	45	41	849	853	857	861	865	869	873	877	881	43	9261

9261 9261

The above *nested magic square* of order 21 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{433, 435, \dots, 447, 449\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{417, 419, \dots, 429, 431, D_{3 \times 3}, 451, 453, \dots, 463, 465\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{393, 395, \dots, 413, 415, D_{5 \times 5}, 467, 469, \dots, 487, 489\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{361, 363, \dots, 389, 391, D_{7 \times 7}, 491, 493, \dots, 519, 521\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{321, 323, \dots, 357, 359, D_{9 \times 9}, 523, 525, \dots, 559, 561\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{273, 275, \dots, 317, 319, D_{11 \times 11}, 563, 565, \dots, 607, 609\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{217, 219, \dots, 269, 271, D_{13 \times 13}, 611, 613, \dots, 663, 665\} \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{153, 155, \dots, 213, 215, D_{15 \times 15}, 667, 669, \dots, 727, 729\} \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{81, 83, \dots, 149, 151, D_{17 \times 17}, 731, 733, \dots, 799, 801\} \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 77, 79, D_{19 \times 19}, 803, 805, \dots, 879, 881\}
 \end{aligned}$$

... (22)

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{3 \times 3} := 1323 & S_{13 \times 13} := 5733 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} := 2205 & S_{15 \times 15} := 6615 \\
 S_{7 \times 7} := 3087 & S_{17 \times 17} := 7497 \\
 S_{9 \times 9} := 3969 & S_{19 \times 19} := 8379 \\
 S_{11 \times 11} := 4851 & S_{21 \times 21} := 9261.
 \end{array}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (22), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 433 + 435 + \dots + 447 + 449 = \left(\frac{449+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{431+1}{2}\right)^2 = 225^2 - 216^2 = 63^2 = 21^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 417 + 419 + \dots + 463 + 465 = \left(\frac{465+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{415+1}{2}\right)^2 = 233^2 - 208^2 = 105^2 = 21^2 \times 5^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 393 + 395 + \dots + 487 + 489 = \left(\frac{489+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{391+1}{2}\right)^2 = 245^2 - 196^2 = 147^2 = 21^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 361 + 363 + \dots + 519 + 521 = \left(\frac{521+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{359+1}{2}\right)^2 = 261^2 - 180^2 = 189^2 = 21^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 321 + 323 + \dots + 559 + 561 = \left(\frac{561+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{319+1}{2}\right)^2 = 281^2 - 160^2 = 231^2 = 21^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 273 + 275 + \dots + 607 + 609 = \left(\frac{609+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{271+1}{2}\right)^2 = 305^2 - 136^2 = 273^2 = 21^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{15 \times 15} &:= 217 + 219 + \dots + 663 + 665 = \left(\frac{665+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{215+1}{2}\right)^2 = 333^2 - 108^2 = 315^2 = 21^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{17 \times 17} &:= 153 + 155 + \dots + 727 + 729 = \left(\frac{729+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{151+1}{2}\right)^2 = 365^2 - 76^2 = 357^2 = 21^2 \times 17^2 \\
 T_{19 \times 19} &:= 81 + 83 + \dots + 799 + 801 = \left(\frac{801+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{79+1}{2}\right)^2 = 401^2 - 40^2 = 399^2 = 21^2 \times 19^2 \\
 T_{21 \times 21} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 879 + 881 = \left(\frac{881+1}{2}\right)^2 = 441^2 = 21^2 \times 21^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.17. *The nested magic square of order 21 formed by 441 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 879, 881\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

- i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 and 19 nested in a magic square of order 21 satisfy Pythagorean triple property, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 63^2 = 225^2 - 216^2 & T_{13 \times 13} &:= 273^2 = 305^2 - 136^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 105^2 = 233^2 - 208^2 & T_{15 \times 15} &:= 315^2 = 333^2 - 108^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 147^2 = 245^2 - 196^2 & T_{17 \times 17} &:= 357^2 = 365^2 - 76^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 189^2 = 261^2 - 180^2 & T_{19 \times 19} &:= 399^2 = 401^2 - 40^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 231^2 = 281^2 - 160^2 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 21 is forth power of 21, i.e., $T_{21 \times 21} := 21^4$;

iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 21^2 \times 3^2 & T_{13 \times 13} &:= 21^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 21^2 \times 5^2 & T_{15 \times 15} &:= 21^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 21^2 \times 7^2 & T_{17 \times 17} &:= 21^2 \times 17^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 21^2 \times 9^2 & T_{19 \times 19} &:= 21^2 \times 19^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 21^2 \times 11^2 & T_{21 \times 21} &:= 21^2 \times 19^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{21 \times 21} &:= T_{21 \times 21} - T_{19 \times 19} = 4 \times (S_{21 \times 21} - S_{19 \times 19}) = 21^2 \times (21^2 - 19^2) = 35280 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 10 \\
 B_{19 \times 19} &:= T_{19 \times 19} - T_{17 \times 17} = 4 \times (S_{19 \times 19} - S_{17 \times 17}) = 21^2 \times (19^2 - 17^2) = 31752 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 9 \\
 B_{17 \times 17} &:= T_{17 \times 17} - T_{15 \times 15} = 4 \times (S_{17 \times 17} - S_{15 \times 15}) = 21^2 \times (17^2 - 15^2) = 28224 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 8 \\
 B_{15 \times 15} &:= T_{15 \times 15} - T_{13 \times 13} = 4 \times (S_{15 \times 15} - S_{13 \times 13}) = 21^2 \times (15^2 - 13^2) = 24696 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 7 \\
 B_{13 \times 13} &:= T_{13 \times 13} - T_{11 \times 11} = 4 \times (S_{11 \times 11} - S_{9 \times 9}) = 21^2 \times (13^2 - 11^2) = 21168 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 6 \\
 B_{11 \times 11} &:= T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 21^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 17640 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 5 \\
 B_{9 \times 9} &:= T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 21^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 14112 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 21^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 10584 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 21^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 7056 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 21^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 3528 = 21^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 21^2 = 441$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 3528 = 21^2 \times 8$.

2.20 Nested Magic Square of Order 22

Example 2.20. Let's consider a nested magic square of order 22 formed by 484 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 965, 967\}$ given by

41	945	25	941	29	937	33	933	37	929	1	947	45	921	49	917	53	913	57	909	61	925	10648
65	845	829	137	833	133	837	839	127	125	103	141	849	851	115	855	111	859	107	863	121	903	10648
901	143	773	209	761	205	765	201	769	197	791	161	777	189	781	185	785	181	789	193	825	67	10648
69	823	755	709	697	269	701	703	263	261	243	273	713	715	251	719	247	723	257	213	145	899	10648
897	147	215	275	653	325	645	321	649	317	667	289	657	309	661	305	665	313	693	753	821	71	10648
73	819	751	691	639	605	597	599	367	365	351	373	609	611	355	615	361	329	277	217	149	895	10648
893	151	219	279	331	375	565	555	415	551	419	411	391	579	387	567	593	637	689	749	817	75	10648
77	815	747	687	635	591	409	535	545	425	421	447	523	443	533	559	377	333	281	221	153	891	10648
889	155	223	283	335	379	561	529	509	461	515	449	513	457	439	407	589	633	685	745	813	79	10648
81	811	743	683	631	587	405	531	503	495	469	475	497	465	437	563	381	337	285	225	157	887	10648
885	159	227	287	339	383	575	541	467	481	491	485	479	501	427	393	585	629	681	741	809	83	10648
905	85	211	229	327	341	385	441	463	489	483	477	487	505	527	583	627	641	739	757	883	63	10648
949	101	175	241	299	349	569	431	451	471	493	499	473	517	537	399	619	669	727	793	867	19	10648
17	869	795	729	671	621	397	429	511	507	453	519	455	459	539	571	347	297	239	173	99	951	10648
953	97	171	237	295	345	573	435	423	543	547	521	445	525	433	395	623	673	731	797	871	15	10648
13	873	799	733	675	625	401	413	553	417	549	557	577	389	581	403	343	293	235	169	95	955	10648
957	93	167	233	291	607	371	369	601	603	617	595	359	357	613	353	363	677	735	801	875	11	10648
9	877	803	737	655	643	323	647	319	651	301	679	311	659	307	663	303	315	231	165	91	959	10648
961	89	163	711	271	699	267	265	705	707	725	695	255	253	717	249	721	245	259	805	879	7	10648
5	881	775	759	207	763	203	767	199	771	177	807	191	779	187	783	183	787	179	195	87	963	10648
965	847	139	831	135	835	131	129	841	843	865	827	119	117	853	113	857	109	861	105	123	3	10648
43	23	943	27	939	31	935	35	931	39	967	21	923	47	919	51	915	55	911	59	907	927	10648

The above nested magic square of order 22 is formed by following distribution entries:

- $D_{4 \times 4} := \{469, 471, \dots, 497, 499\}$
- $D_{6 \times 6} := \{449, 451, \dots, 465, 467, D_{4 \times 4}, 501, 503, \dots, 517, 519\}$
- $D_{8 \times 8} := \{421, 423, \dots, 445, 447, D_{6 \times 6}, 521, 523, \dots, 545, 547\}$
- $D_{10 \times 10} := \{385, 387, \dots, 417, 419, D_{8 \times 8}, 549, 551, \dots, 581, 583\}$
- $D_{12 \times 12} := \{341, 343, \dots, 381, 383, D_{10 \times 10}, 585, 587, \dots, 625, 627\}$
- $D_{14 \times 14} := \{289, 291, \dots, 337, 339, D_{12 \times 12}, 629, 631, \dots, 677, 679\}$
- $D_{16 \times 16} := \{229, 231, \dots, 285, 287, D_{14 \times 14}, 681, 683, \dots, 737, 739\}$
- $D_{18 \times 18} := \{161, 163, \dots, 225, 227, D_{16 \times 16}, 741, 743, \dots, 805, 807\}$
- $D_{20 \times 20} := \{85, 87, \dots, 157, 159, D_{18 \times 18}, 809, 811, \dots, 881, 883\}$
- $D_{22 \times 22} := \{1, 3, \dots, 73, 75, D_{20 \times 20}, 885, 887, \dots, 965, 967\}$

$$\dots \quad (23)$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{array}{ll} S_{4 \times 4} := 1936 & S_{14 \times 14} := 6776 \\ S_{6 \times 6} := 2904 & S_{16 \times 16} := 7744 \\ S_{8 \times 8} := 3872 & S_{18 \times 18} := 8712 \\ S_{10 \times 10} := 4840 & S_{20 \times 20} := 9680 \\ S_{12 \times 12} := 5808 & S_{22 \times 22} := 10648. \end{array}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (23), we get

$$\begin{aligned} T_{4 \times 4} &:= 469 + 471 + \dots + 497 + 499 = \left(\frac{499+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{467+1}{2}\right)^2 = 250^2 - 234^2 = 88^2 = 22^2 \times 4^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} &:= 449 + 451 + \dots + 517 + 519 = \left(\frac{519+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{447+1}{2}\right)^2 = 260^2 - 224^2 = 132^2 = 22^2 \times 6^2 \\ T_{8 \times 8} &:= 421 + 423 + \dots + 545 + 547 = \left(\frac{547+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{419+1}{2}\right)^2 = 274^2 - 210^2 = 176^2 = 22^2 \times 8^2 \\ T_{10 \times 10} &:= 385 + 387 + \dots + 581 + 583 = \left(\frac{583+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{383+1}{2}\right)^2 = 292^2 - 192^2 = 220^2 = 22^2 \times 10^2 \\ T_{12 \times 12} &:= 341 + 343 + \dots + 625 + 627 = \left(\frac{627+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{339+1}{2}\right)^2 = 314^2 - 170^2 = 264^2 = 22^2 \times 12^2 \\ T_{14 \times 14} &:= 289 + 291 + \dots + 677 + 679 = \left(\frac{679+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{287+1}{2}\right)^2 = 340^2 - 144^2 = 308^2 = 22^2 \times 14^2 \\ T_{16 \times 16} &:= 229 + 231 + \dots + 737 + 739 = \left(\frac{739+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{227+1}{2}\right)^2 = 370^2 - 114^2 = 352^2 = 22^2 \times 16^2 \\ T_{18 \times 18} &:= 161 + 163 + \dots + 805 + 807 = \left(\frac{807+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{159+1}{2}\right)^2 = 404^2 - 80^2 = 396^2 = 22^2 \times 18^2 \\ T_{20 \times 20} &:= 85 + 87 + \dots + 881 + 883 = \left(\frac{883+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{83+1}{2}\right)^2 = 442^2 - 42^2 = 440^2 = 22^2 \times 20^2 \\ T_{22 \times 22} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 965 + 967 = \left(\frac{967+1}{2}\right)^2 = 484^2 = 22^2 \times 22^2. \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.18. The nested magic square of order 22 formed by 484 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 965, 967\}$ satisfy the following properties:

- i. The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20 nested in a magic square of order 22 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 88^2 = 250^2 - 234^2 & T_{14 \times 14} &:= 308^2 = 340^2 - 144^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 132^2 = 260^2 - 224^2 & T_{16 \times 16} &:= 352^2 = 370^2 - 114^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 176^2 = 274^2 - 210^2 & T_{18 \times 18} &:= 396^2 = 404^2 - 80^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 220^2 = 292^2 - 192^2 & T_{20 \times 20} &:= 440^2 = 442^2 - 42^2 \\
 T_{12 \times 12} &:= 264^2 = 314^2 - 170^2 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

ii. The entries sum of magic square of order 22 is forth power of 22, i.e., $T_{22 \times 22} := 22^4$;

iii. The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 22^2 \times 4^2 & T_{14 \times 14} &:= 22^2 \times 14^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 22^2 \times 6^2 & T_{16 \times 16} &:= 22^2 \times 16^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 22^2 \times 8^2 & T_{18 \times 18} &:= 22^2 \times 18^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 22^2 \times 10^2 & T_{20 \times 20} &:= 22^2 \times 20^2 \\
 T_{12 \times 12} &:= 22^2 \times 12^2 & T_{22 \times 22} &:= 22^2 \times 22^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

iv. The **borders** entries sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{22 \times 22} &:= T_{22 \times 22} - T_{20 \times 20} = 4 \times (S_{22 \times 22} - S_{20 \times 20}) = 22^2 \times (22^2 - 20^2) = 40656 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 21 \\
 B_{20 \times 20} &:= T_{20 \times 20} - T_{18 \times 18} = 4 \times (S_{20 \times 20} - S_{18 \times 18}) = 22^2 \times (20^2 - 18^2) = 36784 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 19 \\
 B_{18 \times 18} &:= T_{18 \times 18} - T_{16 \times 16} = 4 \times (S_{18 \times 18} - S_{16 \times 16}) = 22^2 \times (18^2 - 16^2) = 32912 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 17 \\
 B_{16 \times 16} &:= T_{16 \times 16} - T_{14 \times 14} = 4 \times (S_{16 \times 16} - S_{14 \times 14}) = 22^2 \times (16^2 - 14^2) = 29040 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 15 \\
 B_{14 \times 14} &:= T_{14 \times 14} - T_{12 \times 12} = 4 \times (S_{14 \times 14} - S_{12 \times 12}) = 22^2 \times (14^2 - 12^2) = 25168 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 13 \\
 B_{12 \times 12} &:= T_{12 \times 12} - T_{10 \times 10} = 4 \times (S_{12 \times 12} - S_{10 \times 10}) = 22^2 \times (12^2 - 10^2) = 21296 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 11 \\
 B_{10 \times 10} &:= T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 22^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 17424 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\
 B_{8 \times 8} &:= T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 22^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 13552 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\
 B_{6 \times 6} &:= T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 22^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 9680 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\
 B_{4 \times 4} &:= T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 22^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 5808 = 22^2 \times 4 \times 3,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 477 + 483 + 485 + 491 = 1936$ are four central values of **nested magic square**. In this case, the fixed difference among the **consecutive borders** is $d_{border} := 3872 = 2 \times 4 \times 22^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 1936$. This gives $5808 - 1936 = 3872$, the same constant value.

2.21 Nested Magic Square of Order 23

Example 2.21. Let's consider a **nested magic square** of order 23 formed by 529 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 1055, 1057\}$ given by

12167

1015	85	81	77	73	69	65	61	57	53	49	45	1021	1025	1029	1033	1037	1041	1045	1049	1053	1057	47	12167
971	927	893	897	901	905	909	913	917	921	925	929	121	117	113	109	105	101	97	93	89	127	87	12167
975	91	855	237	233	229	225	221	217	213	209	205	861	865	869	873	877	881	885	889	207	967	83	12167
979	95	819	787	301	297	293	289	285	281	277	273	793	797	801	805	809	813	817	275	239	963	79	12167
983	99	823	755	727	699	703	707	711	715	719	329	327	323	319	315	311	307	723	303	235	959	75	12167
987	103	827	759	357	383	361	365	369	373	377	673	669	665	661	657	653	671	701	299	231	955	71	12167
991	107	831	763	353	695	427	409	413	417	421	629	625	621	617	613	627	363	705	295	227	951	67	12167
995	111	835	767	349	691	647	591	451	455	459	461	587	583	579	595	411	367	709	291	223	947	63	12167
999	115	839	771	345	687	643	581	563	483	487	489	559	555	567	477	415	371	713	287	219	943	59	12167
1003	119	843	775	341	683	639	585	557	547	539	509	507	543	501	473	419	375	717	283	215	939	55	12167
1007	123	847	779	337	679	635	589	561	517	523	533	531	541	497	469	423	379	721	279	211	935	51	12167
41	125	201	269	333	677	633	593	565	513	537	529	521	545	493	465	425	381	725	789	857	933	1017	12167
39	923	199	267	733	391	435	457	485	553	527	525	535	505	573	601	623	667	325	791	859	135	1019	12167
35	919	195	263	737	395	439	453	481	515	519	549	551	511	577	605	619	663	321	795	863	139	1023	12167
31	915	191	259	741	399	443	449	491	575	571	569	499	503	495	609	615	659	317	799	867	143	1027	12167
27	911	187	255	745	403	447	463	607	603	599	597	471	475	479	467	611	655	313	803	871	147	1031	12167
23	907	183	251	749	407	431	649	645	641	637	429	433	437	441	445	631	651	309	807	875	151	1035	12167
19	903	179	247	753	387	697	693	689	685	681	385	389	393	397	401	405	675	305	811	879	155	1039	12167
15	899	175	243	335	359	355	351	347	343	339	729	731	735	739	743	747	751	331	815	883	159	1043	12167
11	895	171	783	757	761	765	769	773	777	781	785	265	261	257	253	249	245	241	271	887	163	1047	12167
7	891	851	821	825	829	833	837	841	845	849	853	197	193	189	185	181	177	173	169	203	167	1051	12167
3	931	165	161	157	153	149	145	141	137	133	129	937	941	945	949	953	957	961	965	969	131	1055	12167
1011	973	977	981	985	989	993	997	1001	1005	1009	1013	37	33	29	25	21	17	13	9	5	1	43	12167

12167 12167

The above nested magic square of order 23 is formed by following distribution entries:

- $D_{3 \times 3} := \{521, 523, \dots, 535, 537\}$
- $D_{5 \times 5} := \{505, 507, \dots, 517, 519, D_{3 \times 3}, 539, 541, \dots, 551, 553\}$
- $D_{7 \times 7} := \{481, 483, \dots, 501, 503, D_{5 \times 5}, 555, 557, \dots, 575, 577\}$
- $D_{9 \times 9} := \{449, 451, \dots, 477, 479, D_{7 \times 7}, 579, 581, \dots, 607, 609\}$
- $D_{11 \times 11} := \{409, 411, \dots, 445, 447, D_{9 \times 9}, 611, 613, \dots, 647, 649\}$
- $D_{13 \times 13} := \{361, 363, \dots, 405, 407, D_{11 \times 11}, 651, 653, \dots, 695, 697\}$
- $D_{15 \times 15} := \{305, 307, \dots, 357, 359, D_{13 \times 13}, 699, 701, \dots, 751, 753\}$
- $D_{17 \times 17} := \{241, 243, \dots, 301, 303, D_{15 \times 15}, 755, 757, \dots, 815, 817\}$
- $D_{19 \times 19} := \{169, 171, \dots, 237, 239, D_{17 \times 17}, 819, 823, \dots, 887, 889\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{89, 91, \dots, 165, 167, \mathbf{D}_{19 \times 19}, 891, 893, \dots, 967, 969\} \\
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 85, 87, \mathbf{D}_{21 \times 21}, 971, 973, \dots, 1055, 1057\} \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{3 \times 3} := 1587 & S_{13 \times 13} := 6877 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} := 2645 & S_{15 \times 15} := 7935 \\
 S_{7 \times 7} := 3705 & S_{17 \times 17} := 8993 \\
 S_{9 \times 9} := 4761 & S_{19 \times 19} := 10051 \\
 S_{11 \times 11} := 5819 & S_{21 \times 21} := 11109 \\
 & S_{23 \times 23} := 12167.
 \end{array}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (24), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 521 + 523 + \dots + 535 + 537 = \left(\frac{537+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{519+1}{2}\right)^2 = 269^2 - 260^2 = 69^2 = 23^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 505 + 507 + \dots + 551 + 553 = \left(\frac{553+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{503+1}{2}\right)^2 = 277^2 - 252^2 = 115^2 = 23^2 \times 5^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 481 + 483 + \dots + 575 + 577 = \left(\frac{577+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{479+1}{2}\right)^2 = 289^2 - 240^2 = 161^2 = 23^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 449 + 451 + \dots + 607 + 609 = \left(\frac{609+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{447+1}{2}\right)^2 = 305^2 - 224^2 = 207^2 = 23^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 409 + 411 + \dots + 647 + 649 = \left(\frac{649+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{407+1}{2}\right)^2 = 325^2 - 204^2 = 253^2 = 23^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 361 + 363 + \dots + 695 + 697 = \left(\frac{697+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{359+1}{2}\right)^2 = 349^2 - 180^2 = 299^2 = 23^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{15 \times 15} &:= 305 + 307 + \dots + 751 + 753 = \left(\frac{753+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{303+1}{2}\right)^2 = 377^2 - 152^2 = 345^2 = 23^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{17 \times 17} &:= 241 + 243 + \dots + 815 + 817 = \left(\frac{817+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{239+1}{2}\right)^2 = 409^2 - 120^2 = 391^2 = 23^2 \times 17^2 \\
 T_{19 \times 19} &:= 169 + 171 + \dots + 887 + 889 = \left(\frac{889+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{167+1}{2}\right)^2 = 445^2 - 84^2 = 437^2 = 23^2 \times 19^2 \\
 T_{21 \times 21} &:= 89 + 91 + \dots + 967 + 969 = \left(\frac{969+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{87+1}{2}\right)^2 = 485^2 - 44^2 = 483^2 = 23^2 \times 21^2 \\
 T_{23 \times 23} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 1055 + 1057 = \left(\frac{881+1}{2}\right)^2 = 529^2 = 23^2 \times 23^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.19. *The nested magic square of order 23 formed by 529 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 1055, 1057\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19 and 21 nested in a magic square of order 23 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{array}{ll} T_{3 \times 3} := 69^2 = 269^2 - 260^2 & T_{13 \times 13} := 299^2 = 349^2 - 180^2 \\ T_{5 \times 5} := 115^2 = 277^2 - 252^2 & T_{15 \times 15} := 345^2 = 377^2 - 152^2 \\ T_{7 \times 7} := 161^2 = 289^2 - 240^2 & T_{17 \times 17} := 391^2 = 409^2 - 120^2 \\ T_{9 \times 9} := 207^2 = 305^2 - 224^2 & T_{19 \times 19} := 437^2 = 445^2 - 84^2 \\ T_{11 \times 11} := 253^2 = 325^2 - 204^2 & T_{21 \times 21} := 483^2 = 485^2 - 44^2. \end{array}$$

ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 23 is forth power of 23, i.e., $T_{23 \times 23} := 23^4$;*

iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{array}{ll} T_{3 \times 3} := 23^2 \times 3^2 & T_{15 \times 15} := 23^2 \times 15^2 \\ T_{5 \times 5} := 23^2 \times 5^2 & T_{17 \times 17} := 23^2 \times 17^2 \\ T_{7 \times 7} := 23^2 \times 7^2 & T_{19 \times 19} := 23^2 \times 19^2 \\ T_{9 \times 9} := 23^2 \times 9^2 & T_{21 \times 21} := 23^2 \times 21^2 \\ T_{11 \times 11} := 23^2 \times 11^2 & T_{23 \times 23} := 23^2 \times 23^2. \\ T_{13 \times 13} := 23^2 \times 13^2 & \end{array}$$

iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{array}{l} B_{23 \times 23} := T_{23 \times 23} - T_{21 \times 21} = 4 \times (S_{23 \times 23} - S_{21 \times 21}) = 23^2 \times (23^2 - 21^2) = 46552 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 11 \\ B_{21 \times 21} := T_{21 \times 21} - T_{19 \times 19} = 4 \times (S_{21 \times 21} - S_{19 \times 19}) = 23^2 \times (21^2 - 19^2) = 42320 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 10 \\ B_{19 \times 19} := T_{19 \times 19} - T_{17 \times 17} = 4 \times (S_{19 \times 19} - S_{17 \times 17}) = 23^2 \times (19^2 - 17^2) = 38088 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 9 \\ B_{17 \times 17} := T_{17 \times 17} - T_{15 \times 15} = 4 \times (S_{17 \times 17} - S_{15 \times 15}) = 23^2 \times (17^2 - 15^2) = 33856 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 8 \\ B_{15 \times 15} := T_{15 \times 15} - T_{13 \times 13} = 4 \times (S_{15 \times 15} - S_{13 \times 13}) = 23^2 \times (15^2 - 13^2) = 29624 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 7 \\ B_{13 \times 13} := T_{13 \times 13} - T_{11 \times 11} = 4 \times (S_{11 \times 11} - S_{9 \times 9}) = 23^2 \times (13^2 - 11^2) = 25392 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 6 \\ B_{11 \times 11} := T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 23^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 21160 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 5 \\ B_{9 \times 9} := T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 23^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 16928 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\ B_{7 \times 7} := T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 23^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 12696 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\ B_{5 \times 5} := T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 23^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 8464 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\ B_{3 \times 3} := T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 23^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 4232 = 23^2 \times 2^3 \times 1, \end{array}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 23^2 = 529$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 4232 = 23^2 \times 8$.

2.22 Nested Magic Square of Order 24

Example 2.22. Let's consider a nested magic square of order 24 formed by 576 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 1149, 1151\}$ given by

1107	67	1087	63	1091	59	1095	55	53	1101	1103	1129	1083	43	41	1113	37	1117	33	1121	29	1125	25	47	13824
1149	133	1037	117	1033	121	1029	125	1025	129	1021	93	1039	137	1013	141	1009	145	1005	149	1001	153	1017	3	13824
5	157	937	921	229	925	225	929	931	219	217	195	233	941	943	207	947	203	951	199	955	213	995	1147	13824
1145	993	235	865	301	853	297	857	293	861	289	883	253	869	281	873	277	877	273	881	285	917	159	7	13824
9	161	915	847	801	789	361	793	795	355	353	335	365	805	807	343	811	339	815	349	305	237	991	1143	13824
1141	989	239	307	367	745	417	737	413	741	409	759	381	749	401	753	397	757	405	785	845	913	163	11	13824
13	165	911	843	783	731	697	689	691	459	457	443	465	701	703	447	707	453	421	369	309	241	987	1139	13824
1137	985	243	311	371	423	467	657	647	507	643	511	503	483	671	479	659	685	729	781	841	909	167	15	13824
17	169	907	839	779	727	683	501	627	637	517	513	539	615	535	625	651	469	425	373	313	245	983	1135	13824
1133	981	247	315	375	427	471	653	621	601	553	607	541	605	549	531	499	681	725	777	837	905	171	19	13824
21	173	903	835	775	723	679	497	623	595	587	561	567	589	557	529	655	473	429	377	317	249	979	1131	13824
1	977	251	319	379	431	475	667	633	559	573	583	577	571	593	519	485	677	721	773	833	901	175	1151	13824
91	997	177	303	321	419	433	477	533	555	581	575	569	579	597	619	675	719	733	831	849	975	155	1061	13824
1063	1041	193	267	333	391	441	661	523	543	563	585	591	565	609	629	491	711	761	819	885	959	111	89	13824
87	109	961	887	821	763	713	489	521	603	599	545	611	547	551	631	663	439	389	331	265	191	1043	1065	13824
1067	1045	189	263	329	387	437	665	527	515	635	639	613	537	617	525	487	715	765	823	889	963	107	85	13824
83	105	965	891	825	767	717	493	505	645	509	641	649	669	481	673	495	435	385	327	261	187	1047	1069	13824
1071	1049	185	259	325	383	699	463	461	693	695	709	687	451	449	705	445	455	769	827	893	967	103	81	13824
79	101	969	895	829	747	735	415	739	411	743	393	771	403	751	399	755	395	407	323	257	183	1051	1073	13824
1075	1053	181	255	803	363	791	359	357	797	799	817	787	347	345	809	341	813	337	351	897	971	99	77	13824
75	97	973	867	851	299	855	295	859	291	863	269	899	283	871	279	875	275	879	271	287	179	1055	1077	13824
1079	1057	939	231	923	227	927	223	221	933	935	957	919	211	209	945	205	949	201	953	197	215	95	73	13824
71	135	115	1035	119	1031	123	1027	127	1023	131	1059	113	1015	139	1011	143	1007	147	1003	151	999	1019	1081	13824
1105	1085	65	1089	61	1093	57	1097	1099	51	49	23	69	1109	1111	39	1115	35	1119	31	1123	27	1127	45	13824

The above nested magic square of order 24 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{561, 563, \dots, 589, 591\}$$

$$D_{6 \times 6} := \{541, 543, \dots, 557, 559, D_{4 \times 4}, 593, 595, \dots, 609, 611\}$$

$$D_{8 \times 8} := \{513, 515, \dots, 537, 539, D_{6 \times 6}, 613, 615, \dots, 637, 639\}$$

$$D_{10 \times 10} := \{477, 479, \dots, 509, 511, D_{8 \times 8}, 641, 643, \dots, 673, 675\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{433, 435, \dots, 473, 475, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 677, 679, \dots, 717, 719\} \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{381, 383, \dots, 429, 431, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 721, 723, \dots, 769, 771\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{321, 323, \dots, 377, 379, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 773, 775, \dots, 829, 831\} \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{253, 255, \dots, 317, 319, \mathbf{D}_{16 \times 16}, 833, 835, \dots, 897, 899\} \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{177, 179, \dots, 249, 251, \mathbf{D}_{18 \times 18}, 901, 903, \dots, 973, 975\} \\
 D_{22 \times 22} &:= \{93, 95, \dots, 173, 175, \mathbf{D}_{20 \times 20}, 977, 979, \dots, 1057, 1059\} \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 89, 91, \mathbf{D}_{22 \times 22}, 1061, 1063, \dots, 1149, 1151\} \\
 &\dots \tag{25}
 \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 2304 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 9216 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 3456 & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 10368 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 4608 & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 11520 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= 5760 & S_{22 \times 22} &:= 12672 \\
 S_{12 \times 12} &:= 6912 & S_{24 \times 24} &:= 13824. \\
 S_{14 \times 14} &:= 8064 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (25), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{4 \times 4} &:= 561 + 563 + \dots + 589 + 591 = \left(\frac{591+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{559+1}{2}\right)^2 = 296^2 - 280^2 = 96^2 = 24^2 \times 4^2 \\
 T_{6 \times 6} &:= 541 + 543 + \dots + 609 + 611 = \left(\frac{611+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{539+1}{2}\right)^2 = 306^2 - 270^2 = 144^2 = 24^2 \times 6^2 \\
 T_{8 \times 8} &:= 513 + 515 + \dots + 637 + 639 = \left(\frac{639+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{511+1}{2}\right)^2 = 320^2 - 256^2 = 192^2 = 24^2 \times 8^2 \\
 T_{10 \times 10} &:= 477 + 479 + \dots + 673 + 675 = \left(\frac{675+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{475+1}{2}\right)^2 = 338^2 - 238^2 = 240^2 = 24^2 \times 10^2 \\
 T_{12 \times 12} &:= 433 + 435 + \dots + 717 + 719 = \left(\frac{719+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{431+1}{2}\right)^2 = 360^2 - 216^2 = 288^2 = 24^2 \times 12^2 \\
 T_{14 \times 14} &:= 381 + 383 + \dots + 769 + 771 = \left(\frac{771+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{379+1}{2}\right)^2 = 386^2 - 190^2 = 336^2 = 24^2 \times 14^2 \\
 T_{16 \times 16} &:= 321 + 323 + \dots + 829 + 831 = \left(\frac{831+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{319+1}{2}\right)^2 = 416^2 - 160^2 = 384^2 = 24^2 \times 16^2 \\
 T_{18 \times 18} &:= 253 + 255 + \dots + 897 + 899 = \left(\frac{899+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{251+1}{2}\right)^2 = 450^2 - 126^2 = 432^2 = 24^2 \times 18^2 \\
 T_{20 \times 20} &:= 177 + 179 + \dots + 973 + 975 = \left(\frac{975+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{175+1}{2}\right)^2 = 488^2 - 88^2 = 480^2 = 24^2 \times 20^2 \\
 T_{22 \times 22} &:= 93 + 95 + \dots + 1057 + 1059 = \left(\frac{1059+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{91+1}{2}\right)^2 = 530^2 - 46^2 = 528^2 = 24^2 \times 22^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$T_{24 \times 24} := 1 + 3 + \dots + 1149 + 1151 = \left(\frac{1151 + 1}{2} \right)^2 = 576^2 = 24^2 \times 24^2.$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.20. *The nested magic square of order 24 formed by 576 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 1149, 1151\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20 and 22 nested in a magic square of order 24 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{array}{ll} T_{4 \times 4} := 96^2 = 296^2 - 280^2 & T_{14 \times 14} := 336^2 = 386^2 - 190^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} := 144^2 = 306^2 - 270^2 & T_{16 \times 16} := 384^2 = 416^2 - 160^2 \\ T_{8 \times 8} := 192^2 = 320^2 - 256^2 & T_{18 \times 18} := 432^2 = 450^2 - 126^2 \\ T_{10 \times 10} := 240^2 = 338^2 - 238^2 & T_{20 \times 20} := 480^2 = 488^2 - 88^2 \\ T_{12 \times 12} := 288^2 = 360^2 - 216^2 & T_{24 \times 24} := 528^2 = 530^2 - 46^2 \end{array}$$

ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 24 is forth power of 24, i.e., $T_{24 \times 24} := 24^4$;*

iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{array}{ll} T_{4 \times 4} := 24^2 \times 4^2 & T_{16 \times 16} := 24^2 \times 16^2 \\ T_{6 \times 6} := 24^2 \times 6^2 & T_{18 \times 18} := 24^2 \times 18^2 \\ T_{8 \times 8} := 24^2 \times 8^2 & T_{20 \times 20} := 24^2 \times 20^2 \\ T_{10 \times 10} := 24^2 \times 10^2 & T_{22 \times 22} := 24^2 \times 22^2. T_{24 \times 24} := 24^2 \times 24^2. \\ T_{12 \times 12} := 24^2 \times 12^2. T_{14 \times 14} := 24^2 \times 14^2 & \end{array}$$

iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{array}{l} B_{24 \times 24} := T_{24 \times 24} - T_{22 \times 22} = 4 \times (S_{24 \times 24} - S_{22 \times 22}) = 24^2 \times (24^2 - 22^2) = 52992 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 23 \\ B_{22 \times 22} := T_{22 \times 22} - T_{20 \times 20} = 4 \times (S_{22 \times 22} - S_{20 \times 20}) = 24^2 \times (22^2 - 20^2) = 48384 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 21 \\ B_{20 \times 20} := T_{20 \times 20} - T_{18 \times 18} = 4 \times (S_{20 \times 20} - S_{18 \times 18}) = 24^2 \times (20^2 - 18^2) = 43776 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 19 \\ B_{18 \times 18} := T_{18 \times 18} - T_{16 \times 16} = 4 \times (S_{18 \times 18} - S_{16 \times 16}) = 24^2 \times (18^2 - 16^2) = 39168 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 17 \\ B_{16 \times 16} := T_{16 \times 16} - T_{14 \times 14} = 4 \times (S_{16 \times 16} - S_{14 \times 14}) = 24^2 \times (16^2 - 14^2) = 34560 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 15 \\ B_{14 \times 14} := T_{14 \times 14} - T_{12 \times 12} = 4 \times (S_{14 \times 14} - S_{12 \times 12}) = 24^2 \times (14^2 - 12^2) = 29952 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 13 \\ B_{12 \times 12} := T_{12 \times 12} - T_{10 \times 10} = 4 \times (S_{12 \times 12} - S_{10 \times 10}) = 24^2 \times (12^2 - 10^2) = 25344 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 11 \\ B_{10 \times 10} := T_{10 \times 10} - T_{8 \times 8} = 4 \times (S_{10 \times 10} - S_{8 \times 8}) = 24^2 \times (10^2 - 8^2) = 20736 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 9 \\ B_{8 \times 8} := T_{8 \times 8} - T_{6 \times 6} = 4 \times (S_{8 \times 8} - S_{6 \times 6}) = 24^2 \times (8^2 - 6^2) = 16128 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 7 \\ B_{6 \times 6} := T_{6 \times 6} - T_{4 \times 4} = 4 \times (S_{6 \times 6} - S_{4 \times 4}) = 24^2 \times (6^2 - 4^2) = 11520 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 5 \\ B_{4 \times 4} := T_{4 \times 4} - T_{2 \times 2} = 24^2 \times (4^2 - 2^2) = 6912 = 24^2 \times 4 \times 3, \end{array}$$

where $T_{2 \times 2} = 569 + 575 + 577 + 583 = 2304$ are four central values of *nested magic square*. In this case, the fixed difference among the *consecutive borders* is $d_{border} := 4608 = 2 \times 4 \times 24^2$. The expression with $S_{2 \times 2}$ is taken out as we don't have magic square of order 2, but the total entries of order 2×2 give us a good result, i.e., $T_{2 \times 2} := 2304$. This gives $6912 - 2304 = 4608$, the same constant value.

2.23 Nested Magic Square of Order 25

Example 2.23. Let's consider a *nested magic square* of order 25 formed by 625 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 1247, 1249\}$ given by

51	1249	1245	1241	1237	1233	1229	1225	1221	1217	1213	1209	49	53	57	61	65	69	73	77	81	85	89	93	1203	15625
95	1111	181	177	173	169	165	161	157	153	149	145	141	1117	1121	1125	1129	1133	1137	1141	1145	1149	1153	143	1155	15625
91	1067	1023	989	993	997	1001	1005	1009	1013	1017	1021	1025	217	213	209	205	201	197	193	189	185	223	183	1159	15625
87	1071	187	951	333	329	325	321	317	313	309	305	301	957	961	965	969	973	977	981	985	303	1063	179	1163	15625
83	1075	191	915	883	397	393	389	385	381	377	373	369	889	893	897	901	905	909	913	371	335	1059	175	1167	15625
79	1079	195	919	851	823	795	799	803	807	811	815	425	423	419	415	411	407	403	819	399	331	1055	171	1171	15625
75	1083	199	923	855	453	479	457	461	465	469	473	769	765	761	757	753	749	767	797	395	327	1051	167	1175	15625
71	1087	203	927	859	449	791	523	505	509	513	517	725	721	717	713	709	723	459	801	391	323	1047	163	1179	15625
67	1091	207	931	863	445	787	743	687	547	551	555	557	683	679	675	691	507	463	805	387	319	1043	159	1183	15625
63	1095	211	935	867	441	783	739	677	659	579	583	585	655	651	663	573	511	467	809	383	315	1039	155	1187	15625
59	1099	215	939	871	437	779	735	681	653	643	635	605	603	639	597	569	515	471	813	379	311	1035	151	1191	15625
55	1103	219	943	875	433	775	731	685	657	613	619	629	627	637	593	565	519	475	817	375	307	1031	147	1195	15625
1205	137	221	297	365	429	773	729	689	661	609	633	625	617	641	589	561	521	477	821	885	953	1029	1113	45	15625
1207	135	1019	295	363	829	487	531	553	581	649	623	621	631	601	669	697	719	763	421	887	955	231	1115	43	15625
1211	131	1015	291	359	833	491	535	549	577	611	615	645	647	607	673	701	715	759	417	891	959	235	1119	39	15625
1215	127	1011	287	355	837	495	539	545	587	671	667	665	595	599	591	705	711	755	413	895	963	239	1123	35	15625
1219	123	1007	283	351	841	499	543	559	703	699	695	693	567	571	575	563	707	751	409	899	967	243	1127	31	15625
1223	119	1003	279	347	845	503	527	745	741	737	733	525	529	533	537	541	727	747	405	903	971	247	1131	27	15625
1227	115	999	275	343	849	483	793	789	785	781	777	481	485	489	493	497	501	771	401	907	975	251	1135	23	15625
1231	111	995	271	339	431	455	451	447	443	439	435	825	827	831	835	839	843	847	427	911	979	255	1139	19	15625
1235	107	991	267	879	853	857	861	865	869	873	877	881	361	357	353	349	345	341	337	367	983	259	1143	15	15625
1239	103	987	947	917	921	925	929	933	937	941	945	949	293	289	285	281	277	273	269	265	299	263	1147	11	15625
1243	99	1027	261	257	253	249	245	241	237	233	229	225	1033	1037	1041	1045	1049	1053	1057	1061	1065	227	1151	7	15625
1247	1107	1069	1073	1077	1081	1085	1089	1093	1097	1101	1105	1109	133	129	125	121	117	113	109	105	101	97	139	3	15625
47	1	5	9	13	17	21	25	29	33	37	41	1201	1197	1193	1189	1185	1181	1177	1173	1169	1165	1161	1157	1199	15625
15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625

The above *nested magic square* of order 25 is formed by following distribution entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{617, 619, \dots, 631, 633\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{601, 603, \dots, 613, 615, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 635, 637, \dots, 647, 649\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{577, 579, \dots, 597, 599, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 651, 653, \dots, 671, 673\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{545, 547, \dots, 573, 575, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 675, 677, \dots, 703, 705\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{505, 507, \dots, 541, 543, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 707, 709, \dots, 743, 745\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{457, 459, \dots, 501, 503, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 747, 749, \dots, 791, 793\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{401, 403, \dots, 453, 455, \mathbf{D}_{13 \times 13}, 795, 797, \dots, 847, 849\} \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{337, 339, \dots, 397, 399, \mathbf{D}_{15 \times 15}, 851, 853, \dots, 911, 913\} \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{265, 267, \dots, 333, 335, \mathbf{D}_{17 \times 17}, 915, 917, \dots, 983, 985\} \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{185, 187, \dots, 261, 263, \mathbf{D}_{19 \times 19}, 987, 989, \dots, 1063, 1065\} \\
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{97, 99, \dots, 181, 183, \mathbf{D}_{21 \times 21}, 1067, 1069, \dots, 1151, 1153\} \\
 D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 93, 95, \mathbf{D}_{23 \times 23}, 1155, 1157, \dots, 1247, 1249\} \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

In this case, the magic square sums are

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 1875 & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 9375 \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 3125 & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 10625 \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 4375 & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 11875 \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 5625 & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 13125 \\
 S_{11 \times 11} &:= 6875 & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 14375 \\
 S_{13 \times 13} &:= 8125 & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 15625.
 \end{aligned}$$

According to formula (3), and the distribution entries given in (26), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 617 + 619 + \dots + 631 + 633 = \left(\frac{633+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{615+1}{2}\right)^2 = 317^2 - 308^2 = 75^2 = 25^2 \times 3^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 601 + 603 + \dots + 647 + 649 = \left(\frac{645+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{599+1}{2}\right)^2 = 325^2 - 300^2 = 125^2 = 25^2 \times 5^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 577 + 579 + \dots + 671 + 673 = \left(\frac{673+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{575+1}{2}\right)^2 = 337^2 - 288^2 = 175^2 = 25^2 \times 7^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 545 + 547 + \dots + 703 + 705 = \left(\frac{705+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{543+1}{2}\right)^2 = 353^2 - 272^2 = 225^2 = 25^2 \times 9^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 505 + 507 + \dots + 743 + 745 = \left(\frac{745+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{503+1}{2}\right)^2 = 373^2 - 252^2 = 275^2 = 25^2 \times 11^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 457 + 459 + \dots + 791 + 793 = \left(\frac{793+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{455+1}{2}\right)^2 = 397^2 - 228^2 = 325^2 = 25^2 \times 13^2 \\
 T_{15 \times 15} &:= 401 + 403 + \dots + 847 + 849 = \left(\frac{849+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{399+1}{2}\right)^2 = 425^2 - 200^2 = 375^2 = 25^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{17 \times 17} &:= 337 + 339 + \dots + 911 + 913 = \left(\frac{913+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{335+1}{2}\right)^2 = 457^2 - 168^2 = 425^2 = 25^2 \times 17^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{19 \times 19} &:= 265 + 267 + \dots + 983 + 985 = \left(\frac{985+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{263+1}{2}\right)^2 = 493^2 - 132^2 = 475^2 = 25^2 \times 19^2 \\
 T_{21 \times 21} &:= 185 + 187 + \dots + 1063 + 1065 = \left(\frac{1065+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{183+1}{2}\right)^2 = 533^2 - 92^2 = 525^2 = 25^2 \times 21^2 \\
 T_{23 \times 23} &:= 97 + 99 + \dots + 1151 + 1153 = \left(\frac{1153+1}{2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{95+1}{2}\right)^2 = 577^2 - 48^2 = 575^2 = 25^2 \times 23^2 \\
 T_{25 \times 25} &:= 1 + 3 + \dots + 1247 + 1249 = \left(\frac{1249+1}{2}\right)^2 = 625^2 = 25^2 \times 25^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, we have

Result 2.21. *The nested magic square of order 25 formed by 625 consecutive odd natural numbers $\{1, 3, \dots, 1247, 1249\}$ satisfy the following properties:*

- i. *The entries sums of magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21 and 23 nested in a magic square of order 25 satisfy **Pythagorean triple property**, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 75^2 = 317^2 - 308^2 & T_{15 \times 15} &:= 375^2 = 425^2 - 200^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 125^2 = 325^2 - 300^2 & T_{17 \times 17} &:= 425^2 = 457^2 - 168^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 175^2 = 337^2 - 288^2 & T_{19 \times 19} &:= 475^2 = 493^2 - 132^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 225^2 = 353^2 - 272^2 & T_{21 \times 21} &:= 525^2 = 533^2 - 92^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 275^2 = 373^2 - 252 & T_{23 \times 23} &:= 575^2 = 577^2 - 48^2. \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 325^2 = 397^2 - 228^2
 \end{aligned}$$

- ii. *The entries sum of magic square of order 23 is forth power of 23, i.e., $T_{23 \times 23} := 23^4$;*

- iii. *The entries sums are symmetric according to orders of magic squares, i.e.,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{3 \times 3} &:= 25^2 \times 3^2 & T_{15 \times 15} &:= 25^2 \times 15^2 \\
 T_{5 \times 5} &:= 25^2 \times 5^2 & T_{17 \times 17} &:= 25^2 \times 17^2 \\
 T_{7 \times 7} &:= 25^2 \times 7^2 & T_{19 \times 19} &:= 25^2 \times 19^2 \\
 T_{9 \times 9} &:= 25^2 \times 9^2 & T_{21 \times 21} &:= 25^2 \times 21^2 \\
 T_{11 \times 11} &:= 25^2 \times 11^2 & T_{23 \times 23} &:= 25^2 \times 23^2 \\
 T_{13 \times 13} &:= 25^2 \times 13^2 & T_{25 \times 25} &:= 25^2 \times 25^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

- iv. *The **borders** entries sums are*

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{25 \times 25} &:= T_{25 \times 25} - T_{23 \times 23} = 4 \times (S_{25 \times 25} - S_{23 \times 23}) = 25^2 \times (25^2 - 23^2) = 60000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 12 \\
 B_{23 \times 23} &:= T_{23 \times 23} - T_{21 \times 21} = 4 \times (S_{23 \times 23} - S_{21 \times 21}) = 25^2 \times (23^2 - 21^2) = 55000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 11 \\
 B_{21 \times 21} &:= T_{21 \times 21} - T_{19 \times 19} = 4 \times (S_{21 \times 21} - S_{19 \times 19}) = 25^2 \times (21^2 - 19^2) = 50000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 10 \\
 B_{19 \times 19} &:= T_{19 \times 19} - T_{17 \times 17} = 4 \times (S_{19 \times 19} - S_{17 \times 17}) = 25^2 \times (19^2 - 17^2) = 45000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 9 \\
 B_{17 \times 17} &:= T_{17 \times 17} - T_{15 \times 15} = 4 \times (S_{17 \times 17} - S_{15 \times 15}) = 25^2 \times (17^2 - 15^2) = 40000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{15 \times 15} &:= T_{15 \times 15} - T_{13 \times 13} = 4 \times (S_{15 \times 15} - S_{13 \times 13}) = 25^2 \times (15^2 - 13^2) = 35000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 7 \\
 B_{13 \times 13} &:= T_{13 \times 13} - T_{11 \times 11} = 4 \times (S_{11 \times 11} - S_{9 \times 9}) = 25^2 \times (13^2 - 11^2) = 30000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 6 \\
 B_{11 \times 11} &:= T_{11 \times 11} - T_{9 \times 9} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 25^2 \times (11^2 - 9^2) = 25000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 5 \\
 B_{9 \times 9} &:= T_{9 \times 9} - T_{7 \times 7} = 4 \times (S_{9 \times 9} - S_{7 \times 7}) = 25^2 \times (9^2 - 7^2) = 20000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 4 \\
 B_{7 \times 7} &:= T_{7 \times 7} - T_{5 \times 5} = 4 \times (S_{7 \times 7} - S_{5 \times 5}) = 25^2 \times (7^2 - 5^2) = 15000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 3 \\
 B_{5 \times 5} &:= T_{5 \times 5} - T_{3 \times 3} = 4 \times (S_{5 \times 5} - S_{3 \times 3}) = 25^2 \times (5^2 - 3^2) = 10000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 2 \\
 B_{3 \times 3} &:= T_{3 \times 3} - T_{1 \times 1} = 4 \times (S_{3 \times 3} - S_{1 \times 1}) = 25^2 \times (3^2 - 1^2) = 5000 = 25^2 \times 2^3 \times 1,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $T_{1 \times 1} = S_{1 \times 1} = 25^2 = 625$ is the central value of nested magic square. In this case, the fixed difference among the consecutive borders is $d_{border} := 5000 = 25^2 \times 8$.

3 Simplified Procedure

Based on the **nested magic squares** given in Examples 2.22 and 2.23, we can get other cases of lower order appearing in Section 3. This we have done in two main results. One is based on even order nested magic squares and another is based on odd order nested magic squares.

3.1 Even Order Nested Magic Squares

Result 3.1. Below is a distribution of entries appearing in the *nested magic square* of order 24 given in (25) appearing in Example 2.22.

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{561, 563, \dots, 589, 591\} \tag{27}$$

$$D_{6 \times 6} := \{541, 543, \dots, 557, 559, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 593, 595, \dots, 609, 611\} \tag{28}$$

$$D_{8 \times 8} := \{513, 515, \dots, 537, 539, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 613, 615, \dots, 637, 639\} \tag{29}$$

$$D_{10 \times 10} := \{477, 479, \dots, 509, 511, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 641, 643, \dots, 673, 675\} \tag{30}$$

$$D_{12 \times 12} := \{433, 435, \dots, 473, 475, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 677, 679, \dots, 717, 719\} \tag{31}$$

$$D_{14 \times 14} := \{381, 383, \dots, 429, 431, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 721, 723, \dots, 769, 771\} \tag{32}$$

$$D_{16 \times 16} := \{321, 323, \dots, 377, 379, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 773, 775, \dots, 829, 831\} \tag{33}$$

$$D_{18 \times 18} := \{253, 255, \dots, 317, 319, \mathbf{D}_{16 \times 16}, 833, 835, \dots, 897, 899\} \tag{34}$$

$$D_{20 \times 20} := \{177, 179, \dots, 249, 251, \mathbf{D}_{18 \times 18}, 901, 903, \dots, 973, 975\} \tag{35}$$

$$D_{22 \times 22} := \{93, 95, \dots, 173, 175, \mathbf{D}_{20 \times 20}, 977, 979, \dots, 1057, 1059\} \tag{36}$$

$$D_{24 \times 24} := \{1, 3, \dots, 89, 91, \mathbf{D}_{22 \times 22}, 1061, 1063, \dots, 1149, 1151\} \tag{37}$$

From the above distribution, we shall derive even order *nested magic squares* appearing in Section 2.

- i. Subtracting 560 from each member of the distribution given in equation (27), we get the same distribution appearing in Example 2.2, i.e.,

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{1, 3, \dots, 29, 31\}.$$

ii. Subtracting 540 from each member of the distribution given in equation (28), we get the distribution (7) appearing in Example 2.4, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 17, 19, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 53, 55, \dots, 69, 71\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\}. \end{aligned}$$

iii. Subtracting 512 from each member of the distribution given in equation (29), we get the distribution (9) appearing in Example 2.6, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 25, 27, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 101, 103, \dots, 125, 127\} \\ D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{29, 31, \dots, 45, 47, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 81, 83, \dots, 97, 99\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{49, 51, \dots, 77, 79\}. \end{aligned}$$

iv. Subtracting 476 from each member of the distribution given in equation (30), we get the distribution (11) appearing in Example 2.8, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 33, 35, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 165, 167, \dots, 197, 199\} \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{37, 39, \dots, 61, 63, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 137, 139, \dots, 161, 163\} \\ D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{65, 67, \dots, 81, 83, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 117, 119, \dots, 133, 135\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{85, 87, \dots, 113, 115\}. \end{aligned}$$

v. Subtracting 432 from each member of the distribution given in equation (31), we get the distribution (13) appearing in Example 2.10, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 41, 43, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 245, 247, \dots, 285, 287\} \\ D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{45, 47, \dots, 77, 79, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 209, 211, \dots, 241, 243\} \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{81, 83, \dots, 105, 107, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 181, 183, \dots, 205, 207\} \\ D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{109, 111, \dots, 125, 127, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 161, 163, \dots, 177, 179\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{129, 131, \dots, 157, 159\}. \end{aligned}$$

vi. Subtracting 380 from each member of the distribution given in equation (32), we get the distribution (15) appearing in Example 2.12, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 49, 51, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 341, 343, \dots, 389, 391\} \\ D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{53, 55, \dots, 93, 95, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 297, 299, \dots, 337, 339\} \\ D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{97, 99, \dots, 129, 131, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 261, 263, \dots, 293, 295\} \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{133, 135, \dots, 157, 159, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 233, 235, \dots, 257, 259\} \\ D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{161, 163, \dots, 177, 179, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 213, 215, \dots, 229, 231\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{181, 183, \dots, 209, 211\}. \end{aligned}$$

vii. Subtracting 320 from each member of the distribution given in equation (33), we get the distribution (17) appearing in Example 2.14, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 57, 59, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 453, 455, \dots, 509, 511\} \\ D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{61, 63, \dots, 109, 111, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 401, 403, \dots, 449, 451\} \\ D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{113, 115, \dots, 153, 155, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 357, 359, \dots, 397, 399\} \\ D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{157, 159, \dots, 189, 191, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 321, 323, \dots, 353, 355\} \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{193, 195, \dots, 217, 219, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 293, 295, \dots, 317, 319\} \\ D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{221, 223, \dots, 237, 239, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 273, 275, \dots, 289, 291\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{241, 243, \dots, 269, 271\}. \end{aligned}$$

viii. Subtracting 252 from each member of the distribution given in equation (34), we get the distribution (19) appearing in Example 2.16, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 65, 67, \mathbf{D}_{16 \times 16}, 581, 583, \dots, 645, 647\} \\ D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{69, 71, \dots, 125, 127, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 521, 523, \dots, 577, 579\} \\ D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{129, 131, \dots, 177, 179, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 469, 471, \dots, 517, 519\} \\ D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{181, 183, \dots, 221, 223, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 425, 427, \dots, 465, 467\} \\ D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{225, 227, \dots, 257, 259, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 389, 391, \dots, 421, 423\} \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{261, 263, \dots, 285, 287, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 361, 363, \dots, 385, 387\} \\ D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{289, 291, \dots, 305, 307, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 341, 343, \dots, 357, 359\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{309, 311, \dots, 337, 339\}. \end{aligned}$$

ix. Subtracting 176 from each member of the distribution given in equation (35), we get the distribution (21) appearing in Example 2.18, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 81, 83, \mathbf{D}_{18 \times 18}, 581, 583, \dots, 797, 799\} \\ D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{77, 79, \dots, 141, 143, \mathbf{D}_{16 \times 16}, 657, 659, \dots, 721, 723\} \\ D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{145, 147, \dots, 201, 203, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 597, 599, \dots, 653, 655\} \\ D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{205, 207, \dots, 253, 255, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 545, 547, \dots, 593, 595\} \\ D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{257, 259, \dots, 297, 299, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 501, 503, \dots, 541, 543\} \\ D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{301, 303, \dots, 333, 335, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 465, 467, \dots, 497, 499\} \\ D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{337, 339, \dots, 361, 363, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 437, 439, \dots, 461, 463\} \\ D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{365, 367, \dots, 381, 383, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 417, 419, \dots, 433, 435\} \\ D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{385, 387, \dots, 413, 415\}. \end{aligned}$$

x. Subtracting 92 from each member of the distribution given in equation (36), we get the distribution (23) appearing in Example 2.20, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{22 \times 22} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 73, 75, \mathbf{D}_{20 \times 20}, 885, 887, \dots, 965, 967\} \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{85, 87, \dots, 157, 159, \mathbf{D}_{18 \times 18}, 809, 811, \dots, 881, 883\} \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{161, 163, \dots, 225, 227, \mathbf{D}_{16 \times 16}, 741, 743, \dots, 805, 807\} \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{229, 231, \dots, 285, 287, \mathbf{D}_{14 \times 14}, 681, 683, \dots, 737, 739\} \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{289, 291, \dots, 337, 339, \mathbf{D}_{12 \times 12}, 629, 631, \dots, 677, 679\} \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{341, 343, \dots, 381, 383, \mathbf{D}_{10 \times 10}, 585, 587, \dots, 625, 627\} \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{385, 387, \dots, 417, 419, \mathbf{D}_{8 \times 8}, 549, 551, \dots, 581, 583\} \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{421, 423, \dots, 445, 447, \mathbf{D}_{6 \times 6}, 521, 523, \dots, 545, 547\} \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{449, 451, \dots, 465, 467, \mathbf{D}_{4 \times 4}, 501, 503, \dots, 517, 519\} \\
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{469, 471, \dots, 497, 499\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Odd Order Nested Magic Squares

Result 3.2. Below is a distribution of entries appearing in *nested magic square* of order 25 given in Example 2.23.

$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{617, 619, \dots, 631, 633\} \quad (38)$$

$$D_{5 \times 5} := \{601, 603, \dots, 613, 615, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 635, 637, \dots, 647, 649\} \quad (39)$$

$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{577, 579, \dots, 597, 599, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 651, 653, \dots, 671, 673\} \quad (40)$$

$$D_{9 \times 9} := \{545, 547, \dots, 573, 575, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 675, 677, \dots, 703, 705\} \quad (41)$$

$$D_{11 \times 11} := \{505, 507, \dots, 541, 543, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 707, 709, \dots, 743, 745\} \quad (42)$$

$$D_{13 \times 13} := \{457, 459, \dots, 501, 503, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 747, 749, \dots, 791, 793\} \quad (43)$$

$$D_{15 \times 15} := \{401, 403, \dots, 453, 455, \mathbf{D}_{13 \times 13}, 795, 797, \dots, 847, 849\} \quad (44)$$

$$D_{17 \times 17} := \{337, 339, \dots, 397, 399, \mathbf{D}_{15 \times 15}, 851, 853, \dots, 911, 913\} \quad (45)$$

$$D_{19 \times 19} := \{265, 267, \dots, 333, 335, \mathbf{D}_{17 \times 17}, 915, 917, \dots, 983, 985\} \quad (46)$$

$$D_{21 \times 21} := \{185, 187, \dots, 261, 263, \mathbf{D}_{19 \times 19}, 987, 989, \dots, 1063, 1065\} \quad (47)$$

$$D_{23 \times 23} := \{97, 99, \dots, 181, 183, \mathbf{D}_{21 \times 21}, 1067, 1069, \dots, 1151, 1153\} \quad (48)$$

$$D_{25 \times 25} := \{1, 3, \dots, 93, 95, \mathbf{D}_{23 \times 23}, 1155, 1157, \dots, 1247, 1249\}. \quad (49)$$

From the above distribution, we shall derive odd order *nested magic squares* appearing in Section 2.

i. Subtracting 616 from each member of the distribution given in equation (38), we get the same distribution as appearing in Example 2.1, i.e.,

$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{1, 3, \dots, 15, 17\}.$$

ii. Subtracting 600 from each member of the distribution given in equation (39), we get same distribution (6) appearing in Example 2.3, i.e.,

$$D_{5 \times 5} := \{1, 3, \dots, 13, 15, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 35, 37, \dots, 47, 49\}$$
$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\}.$$

iii. Subtracting 576 from each member of the distribution given in equation (40), we get same distribution (8) appearing in Example 2.5, i.e.,

$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{1, 3, \dots, 21, 23, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 75, 77, \dots, 95, 97\}$$
$$D_{5 \times 5} := \{25, 27, \dots, 37, 39, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 59, 61, \dots, 71, 73\}$$
$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{41, 43, \dots, 55, 57\}.$$

iv. Subtracting 544 from each member of the distribution given in equation (41), we get the distribution (10) appearing in Example 2.7, i.e.,

$$D_{9 \times 9} := \{1, 3, \dots, 29, 31, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 131, 133, \dots, 159, 161\}$$
$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{33, 35, \dots, 53, 55, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 107, 109, \dots, 127, 129\}$$
$$D_{5 \times 5} := \{57, 59, \dots, 69, 71, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 91, 93, \dots, 103, 105\}$$
$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{73, 75, \dots, 87, 89\}.$$

v. Subtracting 504 from each member of the distribution given in equation (42), we get the distribution (12) appearing in Example 2.9, i.e.,

$$D_{11 \times 11} := \{1, 3, \dots, 37, 39, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 203, 205, \dots, 239, 241\}$$
$$D_{9 \times 9} := \{41, 43, \dots, 69, 71, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 171, 173, \dots, 199, 201\}$$
$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{73, 75, \dots, 93, 95, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 147, 149, \dots, 167, 169\}$$
$$D_{5 \times 5} := \{97, 99, \dots, 109, 111, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 131, 133, \dots, 143, 145\}$$
$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{113, 115, \dots, 127, 129\}.$$

vi. Subtracting 456 from each member of the distribution given in equation (43), we get the distribution (14) appearing in Example 2.11, i.e.,

$$D_{13 \times 13} := \{1, 3, \dots, 45, 47, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 291, 293, \dots, 335, 337\}$$
$$D_{11 \times 11} := \{49, 51, \dots, 85, 87, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 251, 253, \dots, 287, 289\}$$
$$D_{9 \times 9} := \{89, 91, \dots, 117, 119, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 219, 221, \dots, 247, 249\}$$
$$D_{7 \times 7} := \{121, 123, \dots, 141, 143, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 195, 197, \dots, 215, 217\}$$
$$D_{5 \times 5} := \{145, 147, \dots, 157, 159, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 179, 181, \dots, 191, 193\}$$
$$D_{3 \times 3} := \{161, 163, \dots, 175, 177\}.$$

vii. Subtracting 400 from each member of the distribution given in equation (44), we get the distribution (16) appearing in Example 2.13, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 53, 55, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 395, 397, \dots, 447, 449\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{57, 59, \dots, 101, 103, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 347, 349, \dots, 391, 393\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{105, 107, \dots, 141, 143, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 307, 309, \dots, 343, 345\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{145, 147, \dots, 173, 175, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 275, 277, \dots, 303, 305\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{177, 179, \dots, 197, 199, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 251, 253, \dots, 271, 273\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{201, 203, \dots, 213, 215, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 235, 237, \dots, 247, 249\} \\
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{217, 219, \dots, 231, 233\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

viii. Subtracting 336 from each member of the distribution given in equation (45), we get the distribution (18) appearing in Example 2.15, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 61, 63, \mathbf{D}_{15 \times 15}, 515, 517, \dots, 575, 577\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{65, 67, \dots, 117, 119, \mathbf{D}_{13 \times 13}, 459, 461, \dots, 511, 513\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{121, 123, \dots, 165, 167, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 411, 413, \dots, 455, 457\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{169, 171, \dots, 205, 207, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 371, 373, \dots, 407, 409\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{209, 211, \dots, 237, 239, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 339, 341, \dots, 367, 369\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{241, 243, \dots, 261, 263, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 315, 317, \dots, 335, 337\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{265, 267, \dots, 277, 279, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 299, 301, \dots, 311, 313\} \\
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{281, 283, \dots, 295, 297\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

ix. Subtracting 264 from each member of the distribution given in equation (46), we get the distribution (20) appearing in Example 2.17, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 69, 71, \mathbf{D}_{17 \times 17}, 651, 653, \dots, 719, 721\} \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{73, 75, \dots, 133, 135, \mathbf{D}_{15 \times 15}, 587, 589, \dots, 647, 649\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{137, 139, \dots, 189, 191, \mathbf{D}_{13 \times 13}, 531, 533, \dots, 583, 585\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{193, 195, \dots, 237, 239, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 483, 485, \dots, 527, 529\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{241, 243, \dots, 277, 279, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 443, 445, \dots, 479, 481\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{281, 283, \dots, 309, 311, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 411, 413, \dots, 439, 441\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{313, 315, \dots, 333, 335, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 387, 389, \dots, 407, 409\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{337, 339, \dots, 349, 351, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 371, 373, \dots, 383, 385\} \\
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{353, 355, \dots, 367, 369\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

x. Subtracting 184 from each member of the distribution given in equation (47), we get the distribution (22) appearing in Example 2.19, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 77, 79, \mathbf{D}_{19 \times 19}, 803, 805, \dots, 879, 881\} \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{81, 83, \dots, 149, 151, \mathbf{D}_{17 \times 17}, 731, 733, \dots, 799, 801\} \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{153, 155, \dots, 213, 215, \mathbf{D}_{15 \times 15}, 667, 669, \dots, 727, 729\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{217, 219, \dots, 269, 271, \mathbf{D}_{13 \times 13}, 611, 613, \dots, 663, 665\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{273, 275, \dots, 317, 319, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 563, 565, \dots, 607, 609\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{321, 323, \dots, 357, 359, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 523, 525, \dots, 559, 561\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{361, 363, \dots, 389, 391, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 491, 493, \dots, 519, 521\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{393, 395, \dots, 413, 415, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 467, 469, \dots, 487, 489\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{417, 419, \dots, 429, 431, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 451, 453, \dots, 463, 465\} \\
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{433, 435, \dots, 447, 449\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

xi. Subtracting 96 from each member of the distribution given in equation (48), we get the distribution (24) appearing in Example 2.21, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 85, 87, \mathbf{D}_{21 \times 21}, 971, 973, \dots, 1055, 1057\} \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{89, 91, \dots, 165, 167, \mathbf{D}_{19 \times 19}, 891, 893, \dots, 967, 969\} \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{169, 171, \dots, 237, 239, \mathbf{D}_{17 \times 17}, 819, 823, \dots, 887, 889\} \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{241, 243, \dots, 301, 303, \mathbf{D}_{15 \times 15}, 755, 757, \dots, 815, 817\} \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{305, 307, \dots, 357, 359, \mathbf{D}_{13 \times 13}, 699, 701, \dots, 751, 753\} \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{361, 363, \dots, 405, 407, \mathbf{D}_{11 \times 11}, 651, 653, \dots, 695, 697\} \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{409, 411, \dots, 445, 447, \mathbf{D}_{9 \times 9}, 611, 613, \dots, 647, 649\} \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{449, 451, \dots, 477, 479, \mathbf{D}_{7 \times 7}, 579, 581, \dots, 607, 609\} \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{481, 483, \dots, 501, 503, \mathbf{D}_{5 \times 5}, 555, 557, \dots, 575, 577\} \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{505, 507, \dots, 517, 519, \mathbf{D}_{3 \times 3}, 539, 541, \dots, 551, 553\} \\
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{521, 523, \dots, 535, 537\}
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Final Results

Remark 1. Analysing the results given in Examples 2.1 and 2.23, we can combine both even and order nested magic squares in a single result. The **total sum entries of nested magic squares** are constructed by odd consecutive natural numbers can be written as

$$T_{k \times m} := k^2 \times m^2,$$

where k is the **order of nested magic squares**, and m is the **order of each nested sub-magic square**. See the details below:

For nested magic squares, the total sum entries are given as:

- ▶ order 5, $k = 5, T_{5 \times m} := 5^2 \times m^2, m = 3$ and 5;
- ▶ order 6, $k = 6, T_{6 \times m} := 6^2 \times m^2, m = 4$ and 6;

- ▶ *order 7, $k = 7, T_{7 \times m} := 7^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5 \text{ and } 7;$*
- ▶ *order 8, $k = 8, T_{8 \times m} := 8^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6 \text{ and } 8;$*
- ▶ *order 9, $k = 9, T_{9 \times m} := 9^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7 \text{ and } 9;$*
- ▶ *order 10, $k = 10, T_{10 \times m} := 10^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8 \text{ and } 10;$*
- ▶ *order 11, $k = 11, T_{11 \times m} := 11^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9 \text{ and } 11;$*
- ▶ *order 12, $k = 12, T_{12 \times m} := 12^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8, 10 \text{ and } 12;$*
- ▶ *order 13, $k = 13, T_{13 \times m} := 13^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 \text{ and } 13;$*
- ▶ *order 14, $k = 14, T_{14 \times m} := 14^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 \text{ and } 14;$*
- ▶ *order 15, $k = 15, T_{15 \times m} := 15^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13 \text{ and } 15;$*
- ▶ *order 16, $k = 16, T_{16 \times m} := 16^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 \text{ and } 16;$*
- ▶ *order 17, $k = 17, T_{17 \times m} := 17^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15 \text{ and } 17;$*
- ▶ *order 18, $k = 18, T_{18 \times m} := 18^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 \text{ and } 18;$*
- ▶ *order 19, $k = 19, T_{19 \times m} := 19^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 \text{ and } 19;$*
- ▶ *order 20, $k = 20, T_{20 \times m} := 20^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 \text{ and } 20;$*
- ▶ *order 21, $k = 21, T_{21 \times m} := 21^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19 \text{ and } 21;$*
- ▶ *order 22, $k = 22, T_{22 \times m} := 22^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20 \text{ and } 22;$*
- ▶ *order 23, $k = 23, T_{23 \times m} := 23^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21 \text{ and } 23;$*
- ▶ *order 24, $k = 24, T_{24 \times m} := 24^2 \times m^2, m = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22 \text{ and } 24;$*
- ▶ *order 25, $k = 25, T_{25 \times m} := 25^2 \times m^2, m = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 21, 23 \text{ and } 25.$*

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